

Agro2Circular

D.7.9. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (FINAL)

February 2025

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List of abbreviations

- **A2C** – Agro2Circular
- **CBA** – Collective Bargaining Agreement
- **CE** – Circular Economy
- **CEBM** – Circular Economy Business Model
- **CSR** – Corporate Social Responsibility
- **eLCC** – Environmental Life Cycle Costing analysis
- **ELCA** – Environmental Life Cycle Assessment
- **EMS** – Environmental Management System
- **fsQCA** - Fuzzy sets Qualitative Comparative Analysis
- **GEP** – Gender Equality Plan
- **KVC** – Kveloce
- **LCC** – Life Cycle Costing analysis
- **LCSA** – Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
- **LTIFR** – Lost Time Injury Frequency Rate
- **NEP** – New Ecological Paradigm
- **OSH** – Occupational Safety and Health
- **PM** – Project Manager
- **QCA** - Qualitative Comparative Analysis
- **SR** – Social Responsibility
- **SSH** – Social Sciences and Humanities
- **SO-LCA** – Social Organisational Life Cycle Assessment
- **TCA** – TECNOALIMENTI S.C.P.A.
- **ToC** – Table of Contents
- **UVEG** – Universitat de València
- **UNEP** – United Nations Environmental Programme

Glossary

Description of the Action: In an H2020 project, the DoA is a document that captures the essence of the envisaged solution in the form of high-level needs and features that gives the reader an overview of the final project deliverable(s). It includes the project work plan and information regarding the project scope, cost, time and risks, as well as information such as milestones, deliverables, and project organisation and approach. The DoA contains the project charter and the project work plan of a PM2 project.

Environmental Evaluation (E-LCA). Compilation and evaluation of inputs, outputs, and the potential environmental impacts of a product system through its life cycle and assists in identifying opportunities to improve the environmental performance of products at various points in their life cycle.

Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment (LCSA). Assessment scheme combining three life cycle approaches: Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Life Cycle Costing (LCC) and Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) in a common framework to analyse the complete sustainability performance of the product or process system.

Life Cycle Assessment: LCA is defined by the ISO 14040 as the compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle.

Life Cycle Costing Assessment (LCC). Assessment of all costs related to a product or service within its life cycle, from raw material extraction over production and use until disposal.

Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA). Methodology to assess the social impacts of products and services across their life cycle, delivering systematic data that can be operationalised through quantitative, qualitative and mixed methods.

Social-Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA). SO-LCA can be understood as a social assessment (SLCA) methodology aimed at evaluating the social aspects of production and their potential positive and negative impacts through their lifecycle, at organisation level.

Quadruple Helix Model of innovation. The Quadruple Helix Model of innovation recognizes four major actors in the innovation system: science, policy, industry, and society.

In keeping with this model, more and more governments are prioritizing greater public involvement in innovation processes.

Additional note:

The present deliverable is linked to other project deliverables mentioned in the document. To facilitate understanding, a concise overview of the content of each key deliverable is provided below:

D7.5 – Evaluation framework and methodology (June 2022): *The purpose of this document is to detail the evaluation framework and methodology used to assess the environmental, socio-cultural and socio-economic feasibility as well as the potential impact of A2C systemic solution. The objective of the evaluation is twofold: to assess the environmental, socio-cultural and socio-economic feasibility on the one side, and the potential impact of the Agro2Circular solution on the other side.*

D7.6 – Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Draft) (March 2023): *This deliverable contains the preliminary estimation of the carbon footprint of two product examples in the A2C plastic (chapter 3) and agri-food chain (chapter 4). The study is a screening in which preliminary data is used to evaluate the carbon footprint.*

D7.8 – Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Draft) (March 2023): *The objective of D7.8 is, on the one hand, to provide a first approximation to assess the socioeconomic feasibility of the A2C project and, on the other hand, to estimate the potential impact of the A2C solution considering dimensions at territorial/community level. This screening phase has allowed to pilot the methodologies, indicators and the data gathering procedures, representing a "social thermometer" to the action in the organisations representing the different value chains in the Region of Murcia.*

D7.10 – A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool (September 2024): *D7.10 outlines the process of generating a Multidimensional Model designed for the adoption, replicability, and scalability of circular economy (CE) practices at regional and EU levels. It also introduces a self-assessment tool based on this model, aimed at supporting cities and regions in evaluating their readiness to transition to a CE.*

Executive summary <abstract>

This document constitutes the deliverable 7.9. *Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Final)* and is a summary of the results of the Agro2Circular project undertaken within *task 7.4. Social & economic analysis*. This document is complemented by deliverable 7.7. *Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Final)*.

The objective of D.7.9. is to present the results and main conclusions of the socioeconomic and sociocultural evaluation carried out throughout the life of the project. To achieve this, several methodologies have been applied. The relation between these methodologies is presented in section **2 Evaluation levels rationale**. The results are then presented by levels of analysis, separating them by macro-level (**3 Macro-level evaluation: sociocultural change**) and micro-level evaluation (**4 Micro-level: A2C Life-Cycle Assessment**). The document finalises with a final remarks section where the main conclusions are highlighted.

1 Introduction

Understanding people's awareness and behaviours in the context of the Circular Economy (CE) is essential because individuals are not just passive recipients but active agents of change [1]. Their actions are shaped not only by personal motivations, but also affected by broader organisational and societal structures [2]. This highlights the need for interventions that operate at multiple levels, from individual-focus to broader objectives. In line with this, Agro2Circular (A2C) has developed a systemic approach aimed to identify and assess the environmental, socio-economic, and other key factors—such as governance, regulation, and policy standards—that influence the transition of different actors of the Quadruple Helix towards circularity. By assessing the effects of these factors at different levels, A2C seeks to understand the drivers and barriers to circularity in a holistic manner. This integrated perspective ensures that the circular economy solutions developed within the project will be aligned with both grassroots behaviours and the overarching systems in which they operate. Moreover, A2C has been conceived to bring the socio-economic and environmental dimensions at the core of the systemic circular solution and the current document (D.7.9.) is the final output of this purpose¹. D7.9 is structured in four parts.

1. Evaluation levels rationale.
2. Macro-level evaluation: sociocultural change (results)
3. Micro-level evaluation: A2C Life-Cycle Assessment (results)
4. Conclusions

First, the conceptual explanation of the evaluation levels rationale (5. Evaluation levels rationale), which provides a reminder of the evaluation framework (D.7.5.) and details the methodology followed in the economic and social dimensions of the project. Then, the results of the economic and social evaluations are presented by levels of assessment (6. Macro-level evaluation: sociocultural change & 7. Micro-level evaluation: A2C Life-Cycle Assessment). In each section, the methodology followed by level (macro and micro) is explained in detail. Finally, the fourth and final part contains the conclusions.

¹ Two evaluation exercises, at M18 (screening exercise) and M42 (final evaluation) have been carried out during the project. The main outputs of the screening exercise are *D.7.6. Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Draft)* – VTT & *D.7.8. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Draft)* – KVC. The main outputs of the final evaluation will be: *D.7.7. Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Final)* – VTT & *D.7.9. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Final)* – KVC

The integration of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) disciplines plays a crucial role in the A2C project, particularly within *Work-Package 7 (WP7): A2C systemic solution adoption, replication and scalability*. Indeed, one of the most significant applications of SSH in A2C is the evaluation of its impact, as addressed in *Task 7.4: Social and economic analysis*. However, given the multidimensional nature and sustainability goals of the project, the evaluation extends beyond social and economic dimensions to include environmental aspects. This is covered in *Task 7.3: Environmental assessment, LCA, and A2C circularity monitoring*. The link between these three evaluation dimensions—social, economic, and environmental—was established in *Task 7.2: Evaluation framework*, whose main output was *Deliverable D7.5: Evaluation framework and methodology*. This interconnected approach ensures a comprehensive assessment of the project impacts across all relevant dimensions.

2 Evaluation levels rationale

A2C proposes a systemic solution to the circular economy in the agrifood sector, with a strong focus on public engagement, which means that the four stakeholder groups supporting innovation processes (i.e. Public Administration, Industry, Research and technology institutions and Citizens) are strongly involved in the project activities. A2C moves beyond the organisations themselves, promoting a multi-level approach, aimed at achieving a paradigm shift of the agrifood waste management in the long term. Following this scope, the evaluation logic distinguishes between two levels of evaluation: macro and micro level, represented by a green and a yellow square respectively, as shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure 1 A2C evaluation logic

Source: elaborated by the authors

The **macro-level evaluation** focuses on the systemic impact of the project and its activities across multiple dimensions (environmental, socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding and financial elements, standardization, capacity building and technology, research and innovation), involving various stakeholders (policy makers, government, research community, civil society organisations, business and industry and

education community). The macro-level evaluation has been designed to measure the effects of circular and climate-neutral practices on the different stakeholders involved in A2C, their participation in circular systemic solutions, the development of circular approaches through knowledge transfer, and the replication and visibility of the project solution. Public awareness is an essential element to achieve sustainable development and to involve citizens in circular practices. In A2C public engagement is therefore a core dimension, where all actors are encouraged to participate through the co-creation process. Therefore, the primary goal of the macro-level evaluation is to ensure that public engagement has been effectively achieved. The macro-level evaluation is also closely linked to the Multidimensional Model developed in Task 7.5 (D.7.10) since the regional status of the different model dimensions was analysed through desk research in order to build up the Multidimensional Model and the Self-Assessment tool. In the present deliverable, the results linked with the macro-level evaluation can be found in section 3 Macro-level evaluation: sociocultural change

The micro-level evaluation focuses on the technological dimension and is grounded in the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology, which considers the three pillars (or dimensions) of sustainability: environmental, economic and social. The micro-level evaluation aims to assess the impact of the technological developments achieved during the project across these three dimensions. Each dimension has been evaluated by a dedicated partner (VTT-environmental dimension, UB- economic dimension, KVC-social dimension). Due to the nature of this evaluation, a preliminary screening exercise was conducted during the project (Deliverables 7.6 and 7.8). However, at this stage, the technological solution was not yet fully developed. Now the results of the evaluation on the social and economic dimensions² are included in sections 4.2 LCC implementation and 4.3 SO-LCA territorial systemic solution respectively. **The A2C project combines a systemic, participatory and methodologically sound approach** to address the challenges of the circular economy in the agrifood sector. The integration of macro- and micro-level evaluation, together with an emphasis on public awareness and interdisciplinary collaboration, positions this approach as a comprehensive tool to foster sustainable, inclusive and replicable practices in other contexts.

² The final environmental results are presented in deliverable D.7.7.

In the following sections, the results of the macro-level evaluation and the social and economic assessment at micro-level are presented in detail.

3 Macro-level evaluation: sociocultural change

This section presents the macro-level evaluation in detail, highlighting the sociocultural change created by the project's interventions during its last year. The aim is to assess the effect triggered by the project in participants' awareness, acceptance and behavioural change. The social evaluation of the A2C project goes beyond the LCA evaluation, value chains and technical aspects through a multidimensional approach, with a strong focus on public engagement and co-creation, including citizens and all relevant stakeholders in the process towards circularity.

3.1 A2C Theory of change: from expected to effective outcomes

The Theory of Change (ToC) is a powerful tool to define the planning and implementation of a project or initiative [3]. When used at the design stage, it increases the likelihood that project partners and stakeholders will have clearly identified the intended outcomes of the initiative, the activities that need to be implemented to achieve those outcomes, and the contextual factors that are likely to influence them. The focus of this approach is on the long-term vision of an initiative and is likely to relate to a timescale that lies beyond the timeframe of the initiative, and its aim should be closely linked to the existence of a local, regional or national problem [3].

In A2C, a ToC was developed in Task 7.5 to understand how the project activities would lead to a set of expected results. The aim was to understand how the final impact of the project would contribute to a better understanding of (i) the sustainability factors and (ii) the framework conditions for the applicability of the A2C Multidimensional Model.

In the case of A2C, the identified need was the **urgency of achieving higher levels of sustainability in the agrifood sector**, which determined the defined objective: *the adoption and replication of the circular economy (A2C) model*.

Figure 2 shows the project activities, outputs and outcomes. All elements are based on a needs assessment carried out matching the project's needs with the planned activities that will lead to the expected outputs and intended outcomes along the A2C Multidimensional Model dimensions (See *D.7.10 A2C systemic solution model and self-assessment tool*). This needs assessment and matching with project activities, was approached according to

the dimensions of the Multidimensional Model (technology research and innovation, environmental, socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding and financial and capacity building). This decision was taken to ensure methodological coherence of the activities in WP7.

Figure 2 A2C ToC

ACTIVITIES	OUTPUTS	OUTCOMES
<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Waste collection, including collection, transportation, storage and logistics. 2. Characterisation & conditioning of organic residues (fruit and vegetables) 3. Development of sorting and recycling, and upcycling technologies for multilayer plastics wastes. 4. Extraction and purification of bioactive substances (small & pilot scale) and evaluation for upcycling. 5. Separation of aluminum for multilayer plastic 6. Ensuring water and energy efficiency through the A2C processes 7. Production of a range of new <u>formulations</u> using the bioactive substances extracted from wastes for their application in cosmetic, nutraceuticals and food (small & pilot scale). 8. Recycling of the multilayer plastics coming from agriculture and post-industrial packaging (small & pilot scale). 9. Upcycling of the recycled plastics to obtain high added value materials (small & pilot scale). 10. To obtain standardized bioactive from agrifood waste and plastic materials that can be introduced into industrial processes 11. Integrate the developed technologies at TRL6/7 through demonstrators 12. Developing a Data Integration System for the traceability of materials, predictive tool & public blockchain. 13. Development and implementation of citizen engagement and community-based innovation schemes. 14. Multidimensional evaluation (environmental, economic and social) of the implementation of a systemic circular economy model for the agrifood sector in the Region of Murcia 15. Design and validation of models & tools to support decision making for the adoption of the systemic solution in the region of Murcia <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of <u>financing schemes</u> linked to the business models generated & business cases • Analysis of <u>regulatory and political</u> relevant factors at EU levels • Design of the <u>governance dimension</u> of the systemic solution 16. Design of a self-assessment tool for the replication and the scale up of the A2C model in other regions 17. Capacity building to promote A2C circular model tailored to the innovation helix 18. Networking and clustering [for widespread uptake]. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Waste management plans for collection, transportation, storage, and logistics of the A2C residues (agrifood & plastics) 2. Technologies for the recycling of the organic agrifood wastes, and the sorting, recycling & upcycling of multilayer plastics residues. 3. New A2C standardized products: cosmetics, nutraceuticals, food formulations, agricultural films & food packaging plastics (biodegradable and non-biodegradable). 4. Prototypes of the valorised products (both organic and plastic ones) will be produced at industrial environment. 5. Digital online platform Data Integration System (DIS) for storing, saving, processing and communicating the information across the value chain (private section) and to citizens & general public (public section). 6. Circular Economy Business Models (CEBMs) and associated financing mechanisms and integrating them with natural capital accounting. 7. A2C multidimensional model [governance model, policy, and regulatory model] and self-assessment tool, defining key factors of the relevant dimensions for the adoption of A2C systemic solution, and a roadmap for the replicability and scalability. 8. Recommendations for decision making and replication: policy briefs, financial recommendations, action plans for replication. 9. Scientific articles, Project deliverables, communication, and dissemination materials. 10. Training plan and materials for capacity building of all the stakeholders involved within the systemic solution 	<p>Reduced negative impact of the agro-food sector on the environment.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced CO2 emissions. • Reduced consumption of primary materials (Fossil, Water, Biomass and Metal). • Reduction of waste into landfills • Reduction of water and soil pollution <p>Increased sustainability of the agro-food sector.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of valorised agrifood waste. • Increase water and energy efficiency • Increase of recycled multilayer plastic wastes from primary production sector. • Increase of recycled multilayer plastic wastes from the food processing and manufacturing sector. • Increase traceability of products and processes <p>Raised acceptance, awareness and knowledge among citizens & stakeholders about the circular economy, the importance of reducing food and plastic waste and the relevance of climate-neutral actions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase <u>engagement</u> from all sectors involved in the cluster • Increase consumers and citizens understanding and acceptance of circular and climate neutral practices and to promote their involvement • Increase <u>circular solutions deployment</u> and effective <u>widespread uptake</u> [elaboration of policy and regulation, adoption of circular models and financing programmes...] and high <u>visibility</u> of circular systemic solutions [dissemination materials]

Source: elaborated by the authors

On the **technology, research and innovation dimension** the lack of identification, classification, and sorting techniques in the food waste field as well as a lack of plastic multilayer residues sorting & recycling techniques were identified as the main challenges. The bioactive extraction technologies and the low level of digitalization in the agrifood industry were also detected. Also, the lack of standardized methods in food waste and plastic value chains were acknowledged. On the **environmental dimension**, the lack of environmentally sustainable demonstrated technologies (recycling, sorting, extraction, digitalization) and the need to reduce environmental externalities were clearly identified. The dimensions previously mentioned are of a more technical nature. What was identified on the **social-related dimensions** (socioeconomic, governance, policy and regulatory, funding and financial and capacity building) conditioned the results presented in this section, and are linked with the acceptance, awareness and behavioural change of different groups of stakeholders. The low level of citizens' involvement in circular and climate practices produced a lack of awareness, acceptance, and knowledge related to these practices. In addition, the lack of demonstrated economic sustainability of circular economy techniques and technologies, compounded by market failures arising from the absence of circular value and supply chains, and the lack of viable business models, further hampers progress. Sustainable consumer behaviour adoption remains low, and there is a significant gap in the creation of decent jobs within the circular economy, increasing the risk of exclusion for vulnerable populations in both awareness and consumer adoption. Moreover, a lack of skills and environmental literacy to support the transition to a circular economy model persists. The challenges are exacerbated by insufficient cross-thematic and multistakeholder coordination, ineffective national legislation despite EU directives, and the lack of practices tailored to specific territorial contexts. **Together, these barriers create a complex socio-economic landscape that hinders the advancement of circular and climate change practices.**

Following a comprehensive needs assessment, a series of activities were formulated to address the identified barriers and needs, with a focus on the expected project outputs and outcomes. These activities (the launch of video game contest, and the creation of a community-based scheme in Alhama market, among other activities detailed in section 3.2) were undertaken under WP7 and WP8 and were evaluated using a range of SSH techniques, to assess one of the expected outcomes, namely to *“raise acceptance,*

awareness and knowledge among citizens & stakeholders about the circular economy [...]”.

Understanding people’s awareness and behaviours in the context of the circular economy is essential because individuals are not just passive recipients but active agents of change [4]. Personal behaviours are not only self-motivated but also affected by– and interact with– broader organisational and societal structures. Thus, stressing the need for interventions that operate at multiple levels [4]. In A2C we have focused our study on **the analysis of awareness and knowledge, acceptance and behavioural change of different interventions and their effect on the different groups of stakeholders related to the project.**

3.2 Methodology

Environmental awareness directly influences acceptability by shaping perceptions of need, urgency and effectiveness of environmental solutions. However, economic, social and communication factors also play an important role in this dynamic [5]. Following the community-based participatory research schema, the social impact of A2C interventions was evaluated through mixed methods, as outlined in Table 1 and detailed below.

Table 1 A2C sociocultural evaluation by intervention

A2C responsible partner	Intervention	Tool	Dimensions assessed	Target and sample
PRIMAFRIO	CIRCULAR GAME	INTERVIEW	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	TEACHERS (N=3)
KVC	ALHAMA MARKET	INTERVIEW	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	MARKET VENDORS (N=3)
KVC	ALHAMA MARKET	SURVEY	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	CITIZENS (N=30)
KVC	ALHAMA MARKET PARTICIPATION IN A2C	INTERVIEW	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	PUBLIC AUTHORITIES (N=2)

AGROFOOD & PROEXPORT	MENTORING PROGRAMME PARTICIPATION IN A2C	SURVEY	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	ENTREPRENEURS & BUSNISS (N=8)
KVC	DOMCA DEMO VISIT	SURVEY	Acceptance, awareness, behavioural change	ENTREPRENEURS & BUSNISS (N=9)
KVC	PARTICIPATION IN A2C	SURVEY	Acceptance & awareness	WORKERS (N=74)

Source: elaborated by the authors

The Circular Game, an initiative promoted by PRIMA, was carried out at Murcia and Alhama schools [6]. The objective of the initiative was to develop the technological vocation of students and to promote CE concepts among them³. Five teachers who participated in the initiative were interviewed to obtain feedback on the activity and its impact on the three dimensions studied. The activity had two editions. The teachers were recruited and the interviews conducted by PRIMA, with teachers who participated in both editions at a centre in Murcia (HERMA school), teachers who participated in both editions at a centre in Alhama (CE INF – PRINCIPE DE ESPAÑA) and the company responsible for the training (MMM Academy). The interviews, conducted between July and October 2024, were recorded, transcribed and analysed by KVC using a thematic matrix analysis. Interviewees who were not members of the consortium were required to sign the necessary documents to ensure compliance with data regulations.

The Alhama Market innovation community-based scheme aimed to develop activities to create a society more aware of and committed to the environment and the circular economy. These activities consisted of the collection of food waste from the market stalls to be used by the project, the creation of an information stand to raise awareness and inform citizens and the exhibition of products generated by the project³. The partners in charge of the initiative were PRIMA & KVC, with the collaboration of other partners working in the region (LOLOBIO, EVERSIA, MOCITOS, CETEC, AGROFOOD). Given the relevance of this activity for the project, its impact on several targets was analysed:

³ For more details see deliverable D.7.3. *Public Engagement Strategy & Summary of Activities and Results (Final)*

- **Market vendors:** as waste suppliers and direct participants in the scheme. They have been involved since the beginning of the activity and were accessible for information. Three interviews were conducted to analyse the impact of A2C on their knowledge and attitudes towards CE. The interviews were conducted in December 2024 and were recorded, transcribed and analysed by KVC using a thematic matrix analysis. To ensure compliance with data regulations, interviewees who were not members of the consortium were required to sign the required GDPR protection documents.
- **Public authorities** (INFO & Alhama Town Council): as direct actors in the organisation and implementation of the activity. Although their role in the programme was very active, more information was obtained in the interview in relation to CE in public administration. Two interviews were carried out, recorded, transcribed and analysed by KVC using a thematic matrix analysis. To ensure compliance with data regulations, interviewees who were not members of the consortium were required to sign the necessary GDPR protection documents.
- **Citizens:** as one of the main project targets involved in the final expected outcomes (*“increase consumers and citizens understanding and acceptance of circular and climate neutral practices to promote their involvement”*). In this case a short survey was conducted (30 responses), to obtain feedback on their attitudes and their willingness to consume upcycled products. The questionnaires were carried out by project partners and participants received a sample of a project product as a token of gratitude for their involvement.

The information was collected at different moments. The interviews with the public authorities (INFO & Alhama Town Council) were carried out during September-November 2024 and the interviews with the Market Vendors and the survey to citizens were conducted in the last edition of the market, which took place on December 3rd, 2024.

Mentoring programme and participation in A2C: the AGROFOOD-led mentoring programme aimed to inspire innovations that address the challenges of the A2C model³. The evaluation of this intervention was carried out using a survey designed by KVC and AGROFOOD to obtain feedback on enterprises and entrepreneurs' acceptance of circular business models and on the impact of A2C in their organisations. AGROFOOD and PROEXPORT collected the information and KVC analysed it qualitatively. Not all respondents participated in the mentoring programme but had a relationship (as raw material supplier or new product developer) with A2C, therefore providing valuable insights on their adoption of circular practices (see section 3.3.3 for more details).

DEMO 4 visit: DOMCA organised an open demo visit for entities of the region of Granada to present the A2C results. The attendees (N=9) were universities, companies and researchers who participated in a guided visit through DOMCA's pilot plant. With the

objective of obtaining feedback from the attendees regarding the demo, a survey was designed, conducted and (qualitatively) analysed by KVC.

Effects of A2C on project partners' workers: linked with the SO-LCA, a questionnaire was designed for employees of the companies working on A2C demos. The idea was to collect data for the SO-LCA and information on the effects of participation in A2C on the companies' workers. The questionnaire was designed, conducted and analysed by KVC. Acceptance and awareness were evaluated using the widely accepted New Ecological Paradigm (NEP) indicator as a measure of awareness. [7].

3.3 Social impact assessment of interventions: Framework matrix analysis

The results of the interviews and surveys conducted were analysed using a Framework Matrix Analysis and are presented in *Annex 1. Framework matrix analysis: interventions social impacts evaluation*. The Framework Matrix Analysis is a highly structured approach to analyse qualitative data [8]. A distinguishing feature that differentiates Framework Matrix Analysis from other qualitative methods is the charting of data into a matrix; a spreadsheet which organises interventions in rows and thematic codes in columns. Due to the complexity of the A2C project, information of different stakeholders namely teachers, public administrators, business & entrepreneurs, citizens, market vendors and workers (each of them with their corresponding code, see Table 2) is included in each cell. In the matrix charting process, participants' comments are summarised in spreadsheet cells and classified by themes. By creating this matrix, data is more easily comparable across cases and within individual cases, providing a visually straightforward method to recognise patterns [8]. The information included in this matrix is not limited to interview data, as survey data is also included. The nomenclature of the codes and the samples to which they refer are listed below (Table 2) to facilitate the interpretation of results:

Table 2 Samples characterisation

T0X Target group: teachers (interviews)	
T01	Teacher who participated in the two editions of the competition in the Murcia centre. Graduate in telecommunications engineering, woman, teaching technology in a secondary school for one year.

T02	Entity that delivered the training course (private entity) – <i>two persons participated in the interview</i> . Both with university diploma, a woman and a man, currently working as academy teachers (educational reinforcement in primary, secondary and university), for 9 and 20 years respectively.
T03	Teachers who participated in the two editions of the competition in the Alhama centre – <i>two persons participated in the interview</i> , a woman and a man. Both higher education. A school secretary and a teacher in primary school and 6 th grade tutor. 8 and 30 years of experience respectively.
AP0X Target group: public administration (interviews)	
AP01	INFO – (Instituto de Fomento de la Region de Murcia -Murcia Regional Development Institute) – <i>three persons participated in the interview</i> . Two men and one woman. All with higher education. 28, 34 and 20 years working in the institution respectively.
AP02	Alhama City Council. Degree in economics and MBA, woman, local development agent and 23 years working in this position.
B0X Target group: business & entrepreneurs (surveys N=17) ⁴	
B01 (N=8)	Mentoring programme participants (2 out of 8 respondents participated) and involvement in A2C as raw material supplier or new product developers. The eight respondents have a higher education in agriculture (chemistry or engineering). The majority of the sample is over 40 years old and male. They are mainly in managerial positions, with responsibilities focused on quality, environmental and innovation management in agri-food production and the development of new raw materials and formulations for various industries. The companies are mainly B2B (business to business) and specialise in agricultural production, particularly horticulture (lettuce, melons, watermelons, peppers, tomatoes) and fruit (grapes, nectarines, pomegranates), as well as the use of recycled plastic in intensive farming and applications in confectionery and dairy products. The geographical scope of activity is mainly international and national, most of them being exporters with more than 20 years of experience in the sector.
DEMO01 (N=9)	Target group: stakeholders participating in the DEMO visit The majority of the respondents are male, over 35 years old, with higher education (master or doctorate).
C0 Target group: citizens (survey N=30)	
The majority of respondents were women (73%), over 50 years old. No one was under the age of 16. Most respondents had primary or secondary education, only 7% had higher education (master's or doctorate).	
MV0 Target group: market vendors participating in Alhama market (interviews)	
MV01	Seller and producer of olives and salted meats at the market. 45 years working in the sector.
MV02	Fruit and vegetable seller at the market. Specialised in citrus fruit. 45 years working in the sector.

⁴ 2 out of 8 respondents participated in the mentoring programme

MV03	Seller of tropical fruit seller at the market. Only sells at flea markets. 25 years working in the sector.
W0 Target group: workers in A2C institutions (survey N=74)	
38 men, 35 women, 1 person indicated 'other'. The profiles span roles in management, research and development, laboratory and quality control, technical analysis, administration, and project coordination, highlighting expertise across leadership, innovation, and operational support in diverse sectors. The majority of the sample has higher education and permanent contracts.	
RESEACHER COMMENT	
Comments made by KVC researchers during the analysis of the results to help in the definition of conclusions.	

Source: *elaborated by the authors*

3.3.1 Circular Game

Three interviews were conducted to evaluate the acceptance, awareness and behavioural change associated with this project activity. The key findings are summarized as follows:

The contest-based game design method through programming was highly appealing to all three teachers. They described it as an innovative approach with significant potential for replication, whether in other schools or for addressing different topics.

It was highlighted that this method appeared to produce better results compared to traditional lectures, emphasising its practical nature over the typical theoretical approach.

Additionally, some teachers noted a shift in their perspective regarding the feasibility of implementing such activities in schools: initially sceptical due to limited teaching resources (e.g., time and programming knowledge), in the end the value and practicality of the contest was recognised “[...] *at the beginning I was sceptical, because of the issue of programming and the lack of resources of the students when considering it necessary to have computers at home to be able to develop the training, but the trainers in the end have adapted to the students*”. The initiative was praised as a “*pioneering initiative*,” emphasising its effectiveness in engaging students by using video games to communicate in their language and empowering them to take responsibility for training their peers. “*There has never been anything like the Circular Game*,” T02 remarked. It was also emphasised that tools and technologies used by youngsters should be adopted in the teaching practices.

The activity proved valuable in complementing and increasing teachers’ knowledge of the CE.

A teacher (T01) noted that while their understanding of the CE did not significantly increase, it became more refined and practical (*“It has helped to consolidate the knowledge we already had. We have internalised it more”*). Another (T02), reported a noticeable improvement in his/her knowledge, emphasizing that the game required not only teaching CE concepts but also learning them actively in the process: *“Not only have we had to teach it, but we have had to learn it too”*. It was also highlighted that the greatest challenge to integrating CE into education is the limited time available: *“The determining factor here is time. The teacher’s greatest enemy is time, and perhaps what the Regional Ministry of Education should do would be to make EC part of the curriculum”* (T02). Moreover, they described a transformation in the students’ role and behaviour, moving from passive learners to active agents: *“There are other campaigns to inform them how to recycle, book rotation and garden campaigns, but the pupils are passive and recipients, nothing compared to this project”* (T02).

The interviews revealed several barriers to teaching CE in schools. One key issue identified was that the content is often incomplete and too theoretical, lacking connection to practical actions. This disconnection can result in student misinformation and limited familiarity with circular practices.

The fact that students often exhibit confusion in their behaviour due to contradictory messages received from school and at home (which can hinder the correct implementation of circular practices) was also identified as challenge: *“Here, we give them everything so that they can behave well here, but outside school, if they don’t have that example at home, it creates confusion: they don’t know whether to do what they are taught at school or at home.”* (T03).

Teachers expressed concern that students lack information about the processes and steps that occur after recycling, identifying this as an area for improvement.

This gap in knowledge contributes to a broader lack of public awareness regarding the impact of recycling. Additionally, teachers are uncertain about how effectively the knowledge taught at school is applied at home, as they lack tools or resources to assess whether these practices are being implemented. It was also suggested involving parents to evaluate whether the activities are achieving their intended outcomes.

Most teachers expressed optimism regarding the overall impact of the activity, highlighting its potential benefits. Others, adopted a more critical stance, asserting that the activity fell short of achieving its intended outcomes.

3.3.2 Alhama Market innovation community-based scheme

One of the key findings related to the **acceptance dimension** is the reported satisfaction by market vendors (MVs) and the public administration (APs) in labelling long-standing generational behaviours as circular practices. For instance, AP02 noted that recognising activities such as repurposing excess fruits and vegetables for projects like A2C or feeding livestock animals had provided MVs with a newfound sense of appreciation and acknowledgment that they had not experienced before (“*Yes, you can see that the market vendors are satisfied now that the practice is being named and that they see that it is important. They are happy to do it.*”). Additionally, MV01 expressed a highly positive perception of the project, describing it as a “*beautiful initiative*” that promotes employment and urban cleanliness. Similarly, MV02 supported the continuation and replication of the initiative, emphasising its significant benefits for the local economy.

However, interviews with MVs also highlighted several barriers and challenges associated with the acceptance dimension, primarily linked to economic factors and cultural attitudes toward circular products. Key points include:

- Economic and educational concerns: MV01 suggested that while consumers might be willing to pay a premium price for recycled products, he was critical of efforts to reduce plastic usage. He viewed this as an educational challenge and expressed scepticism about the feasibility of achieving significant plastic reduction in the marketplace.
- Regional resistance: MV02 identified a notable reluctance within the region to embrace recycled products compared to other areas. He attributed this to the dominance of traditional farming practices and economic constraints, contrasting this with a higher demand for eco-friendly products in international markets.
- Pricing challenges: MV02 further emphasized that the higher cost of ecological products limits accessibility, which, in his view, hinders widespread adoption despite a growing environmental awareness among consumers.
- Generational differences: A generational divide in sustainable practices was also evidenced. Older generations were perceived as more reluctant to change, whereas younger generations demonstrated greater awareness and willingness to adopt sustainable behaviours. MV03 noted a gradual shift in consumer habits, such as the use of reusable shopping bags, but stressed that broader behavioural changes

require time to fully materialize. Time, in this context, is considered a critical factor for evaluating the long-term impacts of activities designed to enhance awareness.

Regarding citizens' (C0) acceptance of consuming products made from fruits and vegetables (F&V) waste, 50% of participants agreed with consuming such products, while only 7% strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed were predominantly women over 50 years old with primary or secondary education. Conversely, those who strongly disagreed also fell into the demographic of individuals over 50 with similar educational backgrounds. When considering products made using biodegradable or plant-based plastics, acceptance was even higher: 53% of respondents strongly agreed, while only 7% strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed were primarily women of mixed ages, and the education profile expanded to include individuals with vocational education and training (VET).

Interestingly, citizens displayed greater enthusiasm for upcycled products made from biodegradable or plant-based plastics than from those derived from F&V waste (53% vs. 30%). Comments such as “*not to eat, to use, yes*” suggest that consumers may have trust issues regarding the edibility of products based on F&V waste.

Despite initial concerns, respondents' perceptions of products made from F&V waste improved once they had experienced the products first-hand. Observations from the survey highlight several key findings:

- Many participants expressed a positive attitude toward using products made from food waste.
- Several respondents believed these products contribute to reducing waste, minimizing plastic use, and decreasing environmental impact.
- Participants appreciated the underlying concept and expressed a desire to see such practices adopted more widely.

These findings suggest that while trust and familiarity remain potential barriers, exposure to and awareness of upcycled products can enhance public perception and acceptance over time.

Given the characteristics of the population participating in this initiative, it was important to assess whether respondents fully understood the concept of the CE and their level of awareness (**awareness & knowledge**). According to AP02, market vendors demonstrated awareness of the CE concept, though not necessarily in theoretical terms. Instead, their understanding was reflected through actions, as many had already been independently practicing CE principles (“*Sometimes they don't understand it, when you talk to them about circular economy, they say “what are you talking to me about, what I have left over, to the*

livestock farmer, for the goats". They were already applying it [circular economy] without giving it a name. It is true that, from this [activity in the Alhama Market], and the awareness that has been raised, it is noticeable that there are fewer vegetable waste products in the weekly market.").

Some MVs, such as MV01, indicated that they were already familiar with the topic before engaging in the project and felt that their knowledge had neither significantly improved nor expanded as a result of their participation in the initiative. In contrast, MV02 acknowledged limited initial awareness of CE. However, exposure to the project helped clarify the concept and deepen his understanding of its practical applications. These findings suggest a varied baseline of awareness among participants, ranging from pre-existing knowledge to enhanced comprehension through project involvement. This highlights the value of initiatives that not only encourage CE practices but also strengthen conceptual understanding to foster broader engagement.

Among surveyed citizens (C0), the majority expressed agreement with the potential of recycled food to address food waste. Specifically, 40% strongly agreed, and 47% agreed with this proposition, while only 10% strongly disagreed. Those who strongly agreed were predominantly women, covering various age groups and educational levels, mainly primary or secondary education. Conversely, those who strongly disagreed were also mainly women, aged over 50, with similar educational profiles.

Regarding biodegradable plastic packaging made from plant waste, 37% of respondents strongly agreed that it could help mitigate pollution problems, and 43% agreed. Additionally, 17% neither agreed nor disagreed, and 3% strongly disagreed.

Respondents reported increased knowledge and understanding of these products, particularly their uses and environmental benefits. Some participants noted that while they were already familiar with the information presented, the initiative reinforced their beliefs about sustainability.

However, a few concerns were raised, including:

- The potential presence of pesticides in recycled food products.
- Waste generation during the production process.
- Lack of clarity regarding specific products and their environmental impact.

Understanding people's awareness and **behaviours (behavioural change)** within the framework of the CE is crucial since individuals are active contributors to change [1]. In the case of this initiative, AP02 observed a noticeable reduction in waste following the weekly

market, showing a tangible shift in behaviour. While the level of selective waste collection did not meet initial expectations, market vendors demonstrated increased responsibility by minimizing residues and adopting improved waste management practices. As noted by AP02: *"It is true that, from this, and the awareness that has been raised, it is noticeable that there is less vegetable waste at the weekly market."*

Additionally, participation in community-based innovation schemes such as this activity appeared to influence participants' awareness and behaviours not only in professional contexts, but also in their personal lives. AP02 reflected on this broader impact: *"Work in an activity like this makes you more aware and makes you be much more responsible, even at a personal level, at home."* These findings highlight the dual impact of such initiatives: fostering immediate behavioural changes in specific contexts and cultivating long-term awareness and responsibility in participants' everyday lives.

In terms of consumer (C0) acceptance of upcycled products, 43% of respondents agreed they would purchase products made from F&V waste, while 23% strongly agreed. Conversely, only 10% strongly disagreed, and 13% neither agreed nor disagreed. Those who strongly agreed were predominantly women over 50 years old with primary or secondary education, while those who strongly disagreed were primarily men over 50 with basic education. Regarding the personal actions carried out to prevent food waste at home, the most popular ones included (in order of relevance): checking the fridge/ pantry before buying, considering how food should be stored to keep it fresh, considering the portion sizes and using leftovers. The least popular action was to write down a food plan.

Regarding the incorporation of upcycled products into their routines, responses varied:

- Some participants reported gradually integrating these products, expressing a willingness to adopt them *"little by little."*
- Others already practiced the concept and demonstrated enthusiasm for expanding its use.

However, personal barriers, such as age and ingrained habits, were cited as obstacles to behavioural change despite a positive perception of the idea. Notable preferences also emerged, such as a willingness to use these products for cosmetics but reluctance to consume them as food. These findings highlight both the opportunities and challenges in promoting upcycled products, emphasising the need to address personal barriers and build consumer confidence in using these products across various applications.

Market vendors emerged as the stakeholder group exhibiting the greatest resistance in this dimension. While they expressed a favourable attitude toward expanding such practices in the future, they acknowledged that the current project had not influenced their own behaviour or that of consumers (MV01). This perspective reflects an openness to future change but a lack of immediate action.

As in the other dimensions, some MVs also highlighted resistance to adopting ecological practices, due to their over-reliance on traditional farming methods and the higher costs associated with sustainable alternatives. These factors present significant barriers to implementing circular and sustainable practices within the market context.

Regarding consumer behaviour, MV03 observed a noticeable shift in preferences. Consumers increasingly prioritize purchasing high-quality products in smaller quantities while avoiding F&V with visual imperfections.

As a **final remark and additional information from this activity**, a key observation is the recognition of CE's importance and the role that local development agents can play in fostering these practices. However, significant barriers, such as limited time, resources, and public servant expertise, constrain effective adoption: *“What is most lacking is time and knowledge. The technicians, the Public Administration is quite aged, the workers are older, and they don't have the necessary knowledge”* (AP02).

MVs and AP both demonstrated engagement with CE-related practices but lacked comprehensive understanding of the concept beyond recycling. For MVs, the connection to CE is predominantly linked to individual actions, such as recycling at home and consumers bringing reusable bags to the market. Despite these efforts, economic barriers—particularly the initial investment required—prevent broader implementation of sustainable practices. MVs also noted that consumer preferences for visually perfect and high-quality products challenge the integration of more sustainable alternatives.

Citizens (C0), predominantly older women with basic educational levels, expressed mixed familiarity and motivations toward CE-related products. While 70% of respondents were unaware of the A2C project, many were motivated to consume upcycled products due to environmental and health benefits, alignment with ecological values, and visible progress in product care. Conversely, barriers to consumption included doubts about product quality, unclear pricing, and selectiveness based on personal preferences.

A notable divergence emerged between APs' and MVs' perceptions of the project success. While APs recognised the potential for cost savings through waste reduction, they emphasised the lack of economic incentives for citizens and businesses to make additional efforts. In contrast, MVs showed willingness to engage in future initiatives but indicated that current efforts have not significantly shifted consumer or vendor behaviours.

3.3.3 Mentoring programme and participation in A2C

Figure 3 shows the relationship that survey respondents have with the A2C project (raw material supplier, new product developer) and the instrument by which they got to know the project (stakeholder meetings, dissemination events, mentoring programme, website).

Figure 3 Relation with A2C project

Being involved in A2C has provided the surveyed business with specific knowledge and actionable insights on concrete practices namely:

- By-product management
- R&D&I for new products
- New working systems
- Acquisition of know-how for future projects
- Increased market knowledge

By-product management and R&D&I for new products, were the two more valued options. Just one participant stated that

none-specific actions were implemented in their business after the contact with A2C. This familiarity has influenced the business by an improvement of quality, production or R&D department and by restructuring of work in daily operations. None of the respondents selected the option "*change in the entity's strategic decisions*" and just one of the respondents stated that the actions did not influence their business. In terms of the benefits generated for the company as a result of its participation in or relationship with A2C, the majority of respondents (75%) indicated that no effects had been generated or 'not yet'. Although these types of tangible results require longer periods of time to be evaluated [9], some respondents indicated that an improvement in customer satisfaction, more positive

attitudes/behaviours and better efficiency were some of the results observed after their participation in A2C activities.

Even though 62% of the respondent's knowledge was not improved due to the participation in A2C, participants in the mentoring activity stated that their knowledge was improved "*at the level of mentality, decisions and actions*" and by keeping the same dynamic implemented through the years in CE. It was also remarked that these types of activities were positive as they allow examples to be set, improving the understanding of the CE.

When asked to identify which stakeholder group is most important in accelerating the adoption of the CE, respondents provided a unanimous response, identifying the business sector as the key actor. However, it should be noted that this response may be influenced by the demographic of the respondents, who were exclusively from the corporate sector. The regional and national authorities, along with the European Union, were considered to be equally significant, followed by consumers, universities, and technological centres in descending order. In addition, consensus was reached on the areas where investment should be directed to facilitate the transition from a linear to a CE model. These areas include the qualification of secondary raw materials, followed by research into product design and education. It needs to be noted that the respondents belong to the regional market of Murcia, where the market for secondary raw materials has been identified since the beginning of the A2C research as a hot topic to deploy a CE model.

Although respondents perceive a trend towards more sustainable products, practices, and the use of recycled materials, purchase costs and trust are the factors that have the greatest influence on consumers' willingness to purchase upcycled products.

Regarding the strategies that could be used to generate trust among consumers, general publicity campaigns from public administration and knowledge of legislation on the use and application aimed at companies were the two more valued options. Two more additional strategies were added by the respondents: "*quality comparisons with no recycling*" and "*consumers should not be fooled by false promises*".

One of the most valued strategies for strengthening the adoption of the CE is the identification of collaboration opportunities, which can help expand business lines and drive innovation. Respondents also emphasised the importance of solutions that enhance business growth through CE practices. In terms of current actions being implemented, many businesses have systems in place for the recovery of waste, by-products, and raw materials,

and are actively working on energy management. These efforts reflect a commitment to sustainability within the framework of the CE.

Respondents also highlighted other crucial aspects for the successful implementation of CE in their fields, particularly the recycling and reuse of goods/products and the consumption of products from renewable sources. The overall rationale for these practices is that improved knowledge leads to better production techniques, reduces waste, and enhances transportation and distribution systems. Additionally, it promotes the reuse of by-products in parallel industries and emphasises the importance of information exchange for advancing the CE. However, cultural awareness remains limited among some stakeholders. Despite these positive insights, there are challenges to successfully implement the CE, particularly related to financial resources for investments and personnel costs. Respondents identified challenges such as limited financial investment, insufficient qualifications, and reluctance from clients to share associated costs as significant barriers to progress.

Mentoring programme evaluation (N=2):

The programme effectiveness has been rated with 6 (out of 10) by the respondents. When asked about concrete examples of how the programme impacted positively in the company, the following responses were given:

- *“Expansion of contacts for future contracts or projects”*
- *“More positive attitudes/behaviours towards circular economy products in their business”*
- *“Increased willingness to pay for reused products in their business practices (i.e. value chain inputs, service providers...)”*
- *“Awareness raising among workers”*
- *“Organisation of work to be more efficient”*

According to the barriers and drivers to promote Circular Economy Business Models-CEBM identified in literature [10], the results stated by the respondents are very positive in order to achieve the final intended outcome of the programme, which was to generate innovative results oriented to respond to circular business challenges.

Finally, satisfaction with the mentoring programme in terms of increasing awareness and CE practices acceptance was rated 6,5 out of 10, giving an acceptable rate. As this result was obtained solely from the perspectives of two informants, it would have been beneficial to obtain feedback from the remaining participants.

3.3.4 DEMO 4 visit

This survey was centred on evaluating the generation of informal initiatives for transferring the CE to the work activity of the DEMO 4 visit's participants.

After the visit, most of the respondents (78%) considered that the results presented by DOMCA could be applicable to their activities. The most useful and adaptable results were:

- the presentation of the plan equipment (microwave extraction equipment);
- methodology for extraction of compounds of interest;
- obtaining polyphenols fractions for use as antioxidants.

Other participants stated that their activity was related to consultancy or the academic field and therefore this question was not applicable to them. On average, 43% of the respondents felt that their knowledge of practical ways to reduce food and plastic waste had improved after the visit, by seeing on a pilot scale what is done in the laboratory, by improving their practical knowledge of the technologies used for waste valorisation and by gaining knowledge of extraction methods/ processes. It was also highlighted that some of them had no previous knowledge on the method.

Also, on average, 4 respondents considered that the demonstration could be of interest to their colleagues/ peers in their field or related areas, due to the availability of equipment in which the whole process can be carried out at a larger scale than the laboratory, being of great interest in circular bioeconomy projects. Moreover, the possibility of R&D collaboration and the usefulness of knowing about waste valorisation alternatives were also highlighted.

Showing how the process was scaled up from laboratory to pilot scale was seen as the most useful insight by participants.

3.3.5 Effects of A2C on project partners' workers

Employees of the organisations participating in the SO-LCA assessment were surveyed to evaluate their awareness and acceptance of various recycling-related behaviours. Among the aspects analysed was the workers' awareness of recycling practices. The findings revealed that individuals place significant importance on understanding the destination and purpose of "waste" after it is collected. Two-thirds of respondents (66%) strongly agreed that knowing what happens to items post-collection is essential. This closely aligns with the observations gathered by teachers, who reported that students also expressed a strong

desire to understand the subsequent steps in the recycling process. **These results highlight the critical role of transparency and education in fostering greater engagement with recycling practices.**

The most relevant reason for respondents to correctly separate waste is “to reduce environmental pollution”, followed by “for ethical choices and future generation”. The most significant reason, reducing environmental pollution, underscores a collective concern for ecological preservation. Ethical considerations and the well-being of future generations reflect a strong

Figure 4 Reasons why respondents considered sorting waste correctly important (ranked by importance)

sense of social responsibility, indicating that respondents value long-term impacts over immediate gains.

Additionally, the emphasis on reducing plastic use in food and drink packaging highlights the growing awareness of the detrimental effects of plastic waste. Lastly, the inclusion of economic benefits suggests that while environmental and ethical motivations dominate, practical incentives also play a role in encouraging waste separation.

Employees were also asked how the problem of plastic recycling could be reduced. Table 3 provides insights into respondents’ attitudes towards different strategies to address plastic use. 86% of respondents ("agree" and "fully agree") support reusing existing plastic products. Disagreement (7%) and neutrality (7%) are minimal, suggesting a broad consensus on this approach. The support for the second measure (“*supporting the use of alternative materials at informational, cultural, and economic levels*”) is also high, with 81% ("agree" and "fully agree"). This suggests that respondents value efforts to promote alternatives to plastic. The approach that generated less support was to drastically limit plastic use by law, with only 47% ('agree' and 'strongly agree') supporting it and a significant 28% disagreeing. The higher levels of neutrality (20%) and disagreement suggest reluctance, probably due to concerns about the feasibility or potential consequences of strong legal action. Lastly, informational strategies receive strong support, with 90% ("agree" and "fully agree"). This indicates a widespread belief in the value of education and

awareness-raising as effective tools for driving change. There is no disagreement, highlighting this as a universally accepted strategy.

Table 3 Alternatives for plastic reduction: frequency table

	Reusing plastic products currently on the market	Supporting the use of alternative materials at the informational, cultural and economic levels	Drastically limiting by law their areas of use	Informing consumers and businesses about existing alternatives
Strongly disagree	0%	1%	4%	0%
Disagree	7%	7%	28%	0%
Neutral	7%	11%	20%	11%
Agree	58%	47%	27%	45%
Fully agree	28%	34%	20%	45%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Employees were also asked about the role of authorities regarding recycling practices. The findings shown in Table 4 suggest that respondents favour strategies that enhance convenience and provide tangible benefits, such as more accessible recycling bins and financial incentives.

Table 4 Government actions to facilitate recycling by citizens: frequency table

	More recycling bins	Making recycling bins more accessible	Making recycling bins more visible through signage	Fining the negligent	Suggest reducing the amount of personal waste	Incentivise separate collection with payments/ discounts on the bill
Strongly disagree	0%	0%	1%	4%	5%	0%
Disagree	5%	1%	11%	20%	22%	1%
Neutral	18%	12%	38%	20%	31%	7%
Agree	53%	58%	35%	38%	28%	42%

Fully agree	24%	28%	15%	18%	14%	50%
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Source: elaborated by the authors

Moreover, 50% of respondents reported separating household waste by type, scoring 5 or 6 on the Likert scale. The reasons cited for not separating household waste can be categorised based on their nature and origin:

- Physical and logistical barriers: *“The place where I can take it is far away”, “There are no containers or recycling facilities in my area”*. These barriers highlight structural and access limitations which may discourage even those willing to recycle.
- Personal or household limitations: *“I don’t have space to separate it”, “it’s too complicated”*. These reasons reflect physical space constraints or the perception of effort.
- Lack of motivation or perceived impact: *“I don’t think it has a relevant impact” and “it’s not my responsibility”*. This suggests a disconnection/ lack of awareness regarding the impact of recycling.

The survey results suggest that the primary barriers to recycling, and waste management are logistical rather than stemming from a lack of knowledge or willingness. Most respondents disagreed with the statement, *“I don’t usually recycle because I don’t know how to do it,”* indicating that they are generally informed about recycling practices. Similarly, food waste does not appear to be a significant issue for most participants, as only 1% agreed with the statement, *“Often, my fruit and vegetables look stale, and I throw them away.”* Opinions are more divided on the role of public administration in restricting or prohibiting certain behaviours related to plastic and food waste management. While 43% of respondents “somewhat agree” with such interventions, 38% expressed disagreement to varying degrees. This polarisation suggests that, while many respondents support regulatory measures, others may prefer less restrictive approaches or question their effectiveness.

Overall, the findings highlight the importance of addressing logistical barriers to recycling and balancing public policies to gain broader acceptance.

86% of respondents know the concept of Circular Economy. Considering that respondents work in companies participating in A2C, the percentage is reasonable. Those who answered “yes I know the concept” were asked to define what they think the concept means, and several key ideas emerged from these responses. Based on the responses provided, people generally understand the CE as an economic and production model focused on maximising

resource utilisation, reducing waste, and promoting sustainability through strategies such as reuse, recycling, repair, and renewal. Below are the main ideas derived from the responses:

1. Resource optimisation and waste reduction: *“It is an economic model that seeks to minimise waste and maximise the reuse of resources through repair, recycling, and redesign.”*, *“Maximise recycling of waste as resources and minimise the use of virgin materials.”*
2. Reintegration of waste into the production cycle: *“Giving value to waste and keeping materials and products in circulation for as long as possible.”*, *“A system where energy and raw material consumption is reduced, and what was previously considered waste is utilised.”*
3. Extending the lifecycle of products: *“Making a product reusable as many times as possible and, when it can no longer be reused, recycling it to give it a second life as another product.”*, *“Trying to maximise the use of consumer goods by extending their lifecycle, finding alternative uses, reusing them, and ultimately reducing waste.”*
4. Sustainability-focused and multidimensional approach: *“It is a production model aimed at achieving sustainability at social, economic, and environmental levels.”*, *“Producing goods and services by optimising natural resources and reducing energy consumption”*.
5. Closing production loops: *“Reusing raw materials in new products through recycling or other processes.”*, *“Creating a closed value chain among all agents handling or using a product.”*

Thus, for the majority of respondents, the CE is about reducing, reusing and recycling, integrating waste back into the production cycle, extending the life of products and promoting sustainability.

Respondents were also asked about the perceived quality of different types of products (recycled, remanufactured, repaired, reused ones). The lowest rated were reused products, with 41% of respondents stating that they are of poorer quality than a new product.

Regarding the behaviour of the respondents, the most common actions identified are:

- General Actions: *“I turn off the lights at home when not in use”* appears consistently across all combinations. This suggests that it is the most adopted sustainable practice among respondents.
- Use of reusable bags: *“I take my own bag when I go to the supermarket”* is also a frequent practice, indicating a good awareness of reducing single-use plastics. Moreover, this practice was also noticed and highlighted by the market vendors.
- Replacing with LEDs: *“I have replaced light bulbs with LED lights”* is another prominent habit, related to energy efficiency.

Whereas the less frequent ones are:

- Preferences in packaging: *“I look for food products with easy-to-recycle packaging”* and *“I look for cosmetics and personal hygiene products with biodegradable*

packaging are less common. This may be due to the lack of availability of such products or less awareness of their impact.

- Cosmetics not tested on animals: Although relevant, this appears to be present in a subset of responses, showing that it is not yet a widespread priority.

The last relevant indicator is the New Ecological Paradigm (NEP). This indicator is used to measure individuals' environmental attitudes and their recognition of human dependence and impact on ecosystems, reflecting a shift from anthropocentric to eco-centric perspectives. From the screening exercise [11] to the present assessment stage the average value of the NEP indicator has increased from 48,78 to 55,56 suggesting a change towards values more aligned with a pro-environmental view. The indicator is divided into five factors, which underwent the following changes from the screening analysis to the second wave of evaluation:

- **Limits to growth:** the factor showed a slight increase in the mean score (from 2,95 to 3,06), reflecting a modest rise in awareness of the finite nature of growth, alongside reduced variability (SD), suggesting greater consensus.
- **Antianthropocentrism:** experienced a more pronounced increase in the mean (from 3,36 to 3,86), meaning a stronger rejection of anthropocentric views and a shift towards recognising humanity as part of a broader ecological system.
- **Fragility of nature's balance:** this factor showed a minor increase in the mean score (from 3,84 to 3,88), indicating a stable perception of nature's fragility, with reduced variability pointing to a stronger agreement among respondents.
- **Rejection of exemptionalism:** this factor saw a slight decline in the mean score (from 3,31 to 3,22), which could suggest a decreased inclination to reject the belief that humans are unique and exempt from natural laws.
- **Possibility of an Eco-crisis:** this factor also showed a slight decrease in the mean score (from 3,79 to 3,70), indicating a marginally lower perception of the likelihood of an ecological crisis.

Overall, these results suggest subtle shifts in workers' environmental attitudes, with increased awareness in some dimensions and slight declines or stability in others, reflecting the complexity of changing ecological perceptions.

4 Micro-level evaluation: A2C Life-Cycle Assessment

4.1 Methodology

The final output of the technical evaluation (micro-level) from Task 7.4, focusing on social and economic analysis, is included in this deliverable (*D.7.9: Socioeconomic and Sociocultural Analysis Report - Final*) and is presented in this section. To reach the final output, the following intermediate actions/steps have been carried out (see Figure 5).

Figure 5 A2C Evaluation Timeline

Source: elaborated by the authors

In June 2022, the project evaluation framework was submitted (*D.7.5. Evaluation framework and methodology*). This deliverable gathered all the information related to indicators, methodologies, data collection and timeline of the three evaluations (environmental, economic & social) implemented in A2C in order to assess the impact of the technologies and the systemic solution developments (micro-level evaluation). In March 2023 a first screening exercise (*D.7.8. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Draft)*) was conducted to pilot the methodologies, indicators and the data gathering procedures established by the evaluation framework (D7.5) for the economic and social dimensions within a realistic environment, representing a "social thermometer" to the action in the organisations representing the different value chains in the Region of Murcia. At the time of writing, in February 2025, A2C is coming to an end, so the objective of D.7.9. is the final assessment of the economic and social effects of the technical activities.

The methodological framework for the three deliverables (D7.5, D7.8 and D7.9) is consistent and based on an LCA approach, where each dimension defines its specific goal, scope, targets, and boundaries according to its respective focus. Nevertheless, it is important to acknowledge the shift in methodology from D.7.8 to D.7.9. In the screening analysis it was decided to analyse two value chains (1. Lemon pulp and peels and 2. Disinfection film), in the three evaluations (environmental, economic and social) in order to provide a sneak peak of the technological advancements. These value chains were selected following different selection criteria (TRL level, availability of data, circularity of processes at the regional level) agreed with consortium partners. For this final exercise, and given the maturity reached by the technological solutions, the environmental and economic assessments have been expanded to include additional value chains (for more information see *D.7.7. Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring (Final)* and section 4.2 LCC implementation of this deliverable). The economic evaluation is based on the Environmental Life Cycle Costing (eLCC) perspective (which covers the economic dimension and helps identify hotspots in both cost and environmental impacts) as implemented in the screening exercise. However, due to several methodological limitations (explained below), the scope of the social assessment has been adjusted: instead of grouping organisations by value chain, they have been grouped by type of organisation, namely private for-profit, research organisations and civil society organisations. (see section 4.3.1 Goal & scope). This decision was made for several reasons:

1. Complexity of value chains and unit of analysis: the unit of analysis for the social assessment is the organisation. Given the interrelation between different production lines, analysing organisations grouped by value chain would lead to double counting. A2C is a large-scale project involving 42 partners, most of whom are actively engaged in technological developments and product manufacturing. Analysing all organisations within the context of their respective value chains became unmanageable, especially given the diversity and overlap in their roles.
2. Inconsistencies in comparing organisations within value chains: as outlined in the methodological notes of the screening exercise (D.7.8), value chains in the project include a diverse mix of organisation types—such as SMEs, large companies, associations and foundations. Grouping these distinct entities under the same value chain to perform a comparative analysis against the same standards introduced inconsistencies and methodological incoherence. This diversity necessitated a shift towards grouping organisations from similar nature to enable more meaningful comparisons.
3. Heterogeneity: the contributions and social impacts of the different organisations differ greatly within the same value chain. Grouping organisations by type rather than

value chain allows for a more nuanced analysis of their social contributions and challenges, enabling a clearer understanding of the specific dynamics within each organisational category.

These adjustments aim to address the methodological challenges while maintaining the robustness and relevance of the social assessment.

4.2 LCC implementation

As it was performed in the LCA (see Deliverable D7.6) an eLCC assessment has been conducted on different agri-food demo case studies, which are focused on utilizing waste streams from the agri-food sector.

The objective of the different demos which apply the recycling process is to extract value from waste from its high value bioactive compounds, to produce new foods, nutraceuticals and cosmetics.

In particular, **demo 3** and **demo 4** have been selected to perform an eLCC assessment. The following table reports the output of demo 3 and demo 4 which has been assessed in the eLCC from the processing of different waste input.

Table 5 Different input and output assessed in the agrifood demo 3 and 4 eLCC

DEMO	Input	Output
Demo 3	Lemon waste	Fibers
	Artichoke waste	Phenolic extract
	Broccoli waste	
Demo 4	Lemon waste	Fibers
	Artichoke waste	Phenolic extract

Source: elaborated by the authors

In addition, in conjunction with LCA (see Deliverable D7.6) an eLCC assessment has been conducted on the **plastic chain case study**, which is focused on upcycle plastic residues from the food sector to high added value products. The demo consists of recycling agricultural mulch film waste and waste from aseptic bags produced by the food industry, into new plastic pellet, which can substitute conventional LDPE virgin pellet, currently available on the market.

The next chapters report the results of these eLCC assessments.

4.2.1 Results & conclusions: Agri-food chain – demo 3

The eLCC model has been created on top of the LCA model, in order to assess the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the same input and output included in the LCA model⁵. The next figure shows the same detailed flow chart used for the LCA.

Figure 6 Production chain of enzymatic extraction⁶

The following cost categories have been included in the demo:

1. physical input and output conventional costs (raw materials, energy, water, transport, waste management);
2. equipment costs;
3. labour costs;
4. maintenance costs.

⁵ For a more detailed description of the LCA model, please consult Deliverable D7.6.

⁶ The flow chart is taken from Deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

As it was done in the LCA, all the costs have been allocated between the 2 co-products, the fibre (solid phase) and phenolic extract (liquid phase):

- in those processes where both solid and liquid phases are present (tank and filtration), 75 % of the shared costs are allocated to the solid phase and 25 % to the liquid phase (dry mass allocation);
- costs related to the oven phase are entirely allocated to the solid phase,
- costs related to the concentration and lyophilization phases are entirely allocated to the liquid phase.

The following sections report the life cycle inventories (LCI) of all single processes included in this demo case.

4.2.1.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

As previously reported, the same input/out table used for the LCA has been integrated with the relevant costs, which cover the physical input, such as raw materials, water, energy and transport, as well as the physical output, such as condensed water which is treated as waste. The conventional costs related to each LCA input and output are described in Table 6.

Table 6 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case eLCC

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
agri-food waste (lemon/artichoke/broccoli)	50	kg	45,66	Inbound transportation cost
enzyme	0,005	kg	0,15	
water (boiler feed water)	0,19	m3	0,76	
water (for extraction)	0,15	m3	0,60	
Water (for fibre washing) water	233,6	kg	0,53	Purification process (solid phase)
Oxidising agent	0,69	kg	0,37	Purification process (solid phase)
Electricity (total)	105,6	kWh	14,67	3 months average cost
<i>Electricity (for waste pre-treatment)</i>	1	kWh	0,14	Waste cutting process
<i>Electricity (for the tank)</i>	3,5	kWh	0,49	
<i>Electricity (for filtration)</i>	1,7	kWh	0,24	
<i>Electricity (for the oven)</i>	38,4	kWh	5,34	
<i>Electricity (for concentration)</i>	36	kWh	5,00	
<i>Electricity (for lyophilisation)</i>	25	kWh	3,47	
natural gas	6	m3	27,48	
Output	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
condensed water	0,08	m3	0,025	Waste management cost
carbon dioxide to air	11,13	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)

evaporated water	305,5	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)
discharged water	233,6	kg	0,042	Waste management cost
Fiber (product)	3,6 (from lemon waste) 4,25 (from artichoke waste) 4,2 (from broccoli waste)	kg	-	Recycling process output
Phenolic extract (product)	0,95 (from lemon waste) 0,5 (from artichoke waste) 0,6 (from broccoli waste)	kg	-	Recycling process output

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.1.2 Equipment and installation costs

In order to process the input waste stream, no new equipment is needed. Therefore, no installation costs occur, while equipment costs include the yearly amortisation cost of the existing equipment that is used both for the recycling process, as well for other types of productions. To reflect the proper utilization of the equipment involved in the recycling process, the amortization costs have been allocated on the basis of the total yearly production (in mass), where the cost of the A2C project represents 32%, according to expert judgement from CTNC).

Table 7 reports, per each type of equipment, its amortization cost and the allocated cost to the recycled co-products.

Table 7 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case LCC – equipment costs

Input	Conventional Cost for the whole production (Amortization cost per year ⁷) (EURO)	Conventional Cost for the recycled co-products production (Amortization cost per year) (EURO)
Tank	1450	464
Cutting and homogenising machine	8343	2669,76

⁷ Amortization has been calculated over 8,33 years of use of each equipment. Only 32% of these equipment costs have been allocated to the lemon waste recycling process.

Oven	930	297,60
Filtration equipment	1845	590,4
Freeze dryer/Lyophiliser	8134	2602,88

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.1.3 Labour costs

According to expert judgement from CTNC, to process 150 kg of food waste (from pre-treatment to purification and stabilisation, i.e. the whole process), it takes about 5 days x 8 hours/day x 3 persons, with an hourly cost of 20 €/h.

Since no further information was available, labour cost has been allocated 75% to the fibre and 25% to the phenolic extract.

4.2.1.4 Maintenance costs

Total yearly maintenance costs, for the equipment reported in the use in the process, sums up to 37,000 € per year, while the cost of the A2C project represents 32% (12,000€), according to expert judgement from CTNC. Maintenance cost includes preventive and corrective costs.

Since no further information was available, maintenance cost has been allocated 75% to the fibre and 25% to the phenolic extract.

4.2.1.5 Waste management costs

The food waste recycling process does not produce any solid waste, but only condensed water (from the concentration phase) and the wastewater generated in the fibre washing process, that need to be treated as wastewater. Waste management cost therefore includes the cost of the treatment of condensed water, as already reported in Table 6 as well as the discharged water from fibre washing. Since the concentration phase is entirely dedicated to the production of the phenolic extract, the relative wastewater treatment cost has been fully allocated to the phenolic extract, while, on the contrary, the wastewater treatment cost for the fibre washing process has been fully allocated to the fibre output.

4.2.1.6 Agri-food chain- Demo 3: total eLCC

The current paragraph reports the results of the whole recycling process of the Demo 3 and their co-products, fibre and phenolic extract, including the associated environmental costs, deriving from the application of the Delft University of Technology to the LCA results, with the details per cost category and per life cycle phase. For the environmental externalities, the Delft University of Technology impact assessment method has been applied to the same model and input data used in the LCA.

Environmental Prices is a method developed by CE Delft for expressing environmental impacts in monetary units. The environmental prices are available for the following impact categories:

- Climate change (kg CO₂ eq)
- Ozone depletion (kg CFC-11 eq)
- Terrestrial acidification (kg SO₂ eq)
- Freshwater eutrophication (kg P eq)
- Marine eutrophication (kg N eq)
- Human toxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq)
- Photochemical oxidant formation (kg NMVOC)
- Particulate matter formation (kg PM10 eq)
- Terrestrial ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq)
- Freshwater ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq)
- Marine ecotoxicity (kg 1,4-DB eq)
- Ionising radiation (kBq U235 eq)
- Agricultural land occupation (m²a)
- Urban land occupation (m²a)
- Natural land transformation (m²)
- Water depletion (m³)
- Metal depletion (kg Fe eq)
- Fossil depletion (kg oil eq)

The tables and figures below show the results of the eLCC assessment of the production of 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract from, respectively, recycled lemon waste, artichoke waste and broccoli waste. From these tables and figures, it is evident that for both co-products, the total eLCC is driven by the conventional cost, which represents approximately 99% of the overall costs both for the fibre and the phenolic extract.

For the fibre, personnel costs and maintenance costs are the largest contributors, followed by equipment costs, while for the phenolic extract equipment costs and personnel costs, followed by maintenance costs, are the largest contributors.

Since only the output yield varies among the 3 different types of agrifood waste, the cost structure is the same for all these waste streams and the only difference is the total eLCC cost per kg of output.

Table 8 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	-	0,17	-	1,48	1,69	0,5%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	6,54	-	-	6,54	1,8%
Equipment cost	25,43	-	10,04	-	3,31	38,77	10,6%
Maintenance cost	-	114,29	-	-	-	114,29	31,3%
Personnel cost	-	190,48	-	-	-	190,48	52,2%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,04	0,36	-	0,40	0,1%
Transport cost	10,87	-	-	-	-	10,87	3,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	0,02	-	-	0,01	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,32	0,26	-	0,47	0,2%
Total conventional cost	36,33	304,76	17,12	0,64	4,79	363,64	99,7%
Environmental costs	0,02	-	0,38	0,05	0,61	1,05	0,3%
Total eLCC	36,35	304,76	17,50	0,69	5,40	364,69	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 9 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,02	-	0,11	5,43	3,66	9,22	2,6%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	4,13	-	-	4,13	1,2%
Equipment cost	16,06	-	6,34	-	109,59	132,00	37,8%
Maintenance cost	-	72,18	-	-	-	72,18	20,7%
Personnel cost	-	120,30	-	-	-	120,30	34,5%

Raw materials cost	-	-	0,02	-	-	0,02	0,0%
Transport cost	6,87	-	-	-	-	6,87	2,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	0,03	-	0,03	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,20	-	-	0,20	0,1%
Total conventional cost	22,95	192,48	10,81	5,46	113,25	344,95	98,9%
Environmental costs	0,01	-	0,24	2,24	1,50	3,98	1,1%
Total eLCC	22,96	192,48	11,05	7,70	114,75	348,93	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 10 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled artichoke waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	-	0,15	-	1,26	1,43	0,5%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	5,54	-	-	5,54	1,8%
Equipment cost	21,54	-	8,51	-	2,80	32,84	10,6%
Maintenance cost	-	96,81	-	-	-	96,81	31,3%
Personnel cost	-	161,34	-	-	-	161,34	52,2%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,03	0,30	-	0,34	0,1%
Transport cost	9,21	-	-	-	-	9,21	3,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	0,02	-	0,02	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,27	0,22	-	0,49	0,2%
Total conventional cost	30,78	258,15	14,50	0,54	4,06	308,03	99,7%
Environmental costs	0,01	-	0,32	0,04	0,51	0,89	0,3%
Total eLCC	30,79	258,15	14,82	0,59	4,57	308,92	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 11 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled artichoke waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,04	-	0,21	10,32	6,95	17,51	2,6%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	7,85	-	-	7,85	1,2%
Equipment cost	30,51	-	12,05	-	208,23	250,79	37,8%
Maintenance cost	-	137,14	-	-	-	137,14	20,7%
Personnel cost	-	228,57	-	-	-	228,57	34,5%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,04	-	-	0,04	0,0%
Transport cost	13,05	-	-	-	-	13,05	2,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	0,05	-	0,05	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,39	-	-	0,39	0,1%
Total conventional cost	43,60	365,71	20,54	10,37	215,18	655,40	98,9%
Environmental costs	0,02	-	0,45	4,26	2,84	7,57	1,1%
Total eLCC	43,62	365,71	20,99	14,62	218,02	662,97	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 12 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled broccoli waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	-	0,15	-	1,27	1,45	0,5%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	5,61	-	-	5,61	1,8%
Equipment cost	21,79	-	8,61	-	2,83	33,24	10,6%
Maintenance cost	-	97,96	-	-	-	97,96	31,3%
Personnel cost	-	163,27	-	-	-	163,27	52,2%

Raw materials cost	-	-	0,03	0,31	-	0,34	0,1%
Transport cost	9,32	-	-	-	-	9,32	3,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	0,02	-	0,02	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,28	0,22	-	0,50	0,2%
Total conventional cost	31,14	261,22	14,67	0,55	4,10	311,69	99,7%
Environmental costs	0,01	-	0,32	0,04	0,52	0,90	0,3%
Total eLCC	31,16	261,22	15,00	0,59	4,62	312,59	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 13 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled broccoli waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection&pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction&filtration	Recycling process - purification	Recycling process - stabilization	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	-	0,17	8,60	5,79	14,59	2,6%
Energy cost - thermal energy	-	-	6,54	-	-	6,54	1,2%
Equipment cost	25,43	-	10,04	-	173,53	208,99	37,8%
Maintenance cost	-	114,29	-	-	-	114,29	20,7%
Personnel cost	-	190,48	-	-	-	190,48	34,5%
Raw materials cost	-	-	0,04	-	-	0,04	0,0%
Transport cost	10,87	-	-	-	-	10,87	2,0%
Waste management cost	-	-	-	0,04	-	0,04	0,0%
Water cost	-	-	0,32	-	-	0,32	0,1%
Total conventional cost	36,33	304,76	17,12	8,64	179,32	546,17	98,9%
Environmental costs	0,02	-	0,38	3,55	2,37	6,31	1,1%
Total eLCC	36,35	304,76	17,50	12,19	181,68	552,48	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 7 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fibre from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 8 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 11 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fibre from broccoli waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 12 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of phenolic extract from broccoli waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Focusing on the conventional costs, Figure 13 and Figure 14 clearly show the % contribution of each type of cost to the total conventional costs (the thickness of the arrow is proportional to its impact). For the fibre, Personnel cost represents more than 50% of the total conventional costs, while maintenance costs bring an additional 31%. For the phenolic extract the contribution of personnel and maintenance is still highly significant, but lower, being, respectively, 34% and 20%. For the phenolic extract, the cost of the lyophilisation equipment is significant as well, representing 31% of the total conventional cost.

Figure 13 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of fibre from lemon waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 14 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 15 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of fibre from artichoke waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 16 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from artichoke waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 17 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of fibre from broccoli waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 18 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from broccoli waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Personnel cost, as well as maintenance and equipment cost, are highly influenced by the demo testing small scale, which prevents the recycling process from achieving a high level

of efficiency. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis has been conducted to assess how the total cost would change if a higher scale and higher efficiency were applied. According to CTNC expert judgment, the current equipment set could treat up to 7500 kg of food waste input, instead of the 1250 kg assessed in the default scenario. Moreover, the increased efficiency could bring scale economy to personnel cost, as well as maintenance and equipment cost. Personnel hours, according to CTNC expert judgment, could be cut by 50%, dropping from the default 120 hours⁸ per 150 kg of food waste input, to 60 hours to treat the same amount. Table 14 reports the main assumption for the default and the alternative scenario assessed in the sensitivity analysis.

Table 14 Default and alternative scenarios main assumptions – fibre and phenolic extract from lemon waste

Default scenario	Default scenario	Alternative scenario
Fiber & Phenolic extract	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 120 hours of personnel per 150 kg of lemon waste input 1250 kg of food waste input yearly treated 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 60 hours of personnel per 150 kg of lemon waste input 7500 kg of food waste input yearly treated

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 19 and Figure 20, and Table 15 and Table 16 show the results of the total eLCC assumptions for 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste, which has been selected as representative also for other type of food wastes, being the assumptions the same for all waste streams. From the sensitivity analysis it is evident the considerable cost reduction for both co-products, as the fibre cost is reduced by 61% and the phenolic extract by 59%, thanks to a reduction in maintenance and equipment costs (-83%) and in personnel cost (-50%).

⁸ It was assumed that it takes about 5 days* 8 hours/day * 3 persons to treat 150 kg of lemon waste input.

Figure 19 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - fibre from lemon waste - sensitivity analysis

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 15 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	1,69	1,69	0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	6,54	6,54	0%
Equipment cost	38,77	6,46	-83%
Maintenance cost	114,29	19,05	-83%
Personnel cost	190,48	95,24	-50%
Raw materials cost	0,40	0,40	0%
Transport cost	10,87	10,87	0%
Waste management cost	0,02	0,02	0%
Water cost	0,58	0,58	0%
Total conventional cost	363,64	140,85	-61%
Environmental costs	1,05	1,05	0%
Total eLCC	364,69	141,90	-61%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 20 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - phenolic extract from lemon waste - sensitivity analysis

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 16 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	9,22	9,22	0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	4,13	4,13	0%
Equipment cost	132,00	22,00	-83%
Maintenance cost	72,18	12,03	-83%
Personnel cost	120,30	60,15	-50%
Raw materials cost	0,02	0,02	0%
Transport cost	6,87	6,87	0%
Waste management cost	0,03	0,03	0%
Water cost	0,20	0,20	0%
Total conventional cost	344,95	114,65	-67%
Environmental costs	3,98	3,98	0%
Total eLCC	348,93	118,63	-66%

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.1.7 Agri-food recycled products vs conventional products: demo 3

This section focuses on a possible comparison of the total eLCC assessment of the fibre and the phenolic extract from recycled food waste, against conventional (virgin) products that could be considered as alternative products already available.

Since the function of both the fibre and the phenolic extract is not yet fully defined, given that these substances can be included in a wide range of different formulations, the identification of possible benchmark products is still uncertain. For the phenolic extract, which is rich in antioxidant compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids), currently there is no proper reference product, since there is no nutritional claim on polyphenols or antioxidant capacity. In the LCA, some benchmark products have been investigated, as reported in the next table. Unfortunately, the conventional cost was not available for the whole list of products. On the contrary, for quercetin, only the conventional cost was provided Table 17.

Table 17 Potential benchmark products for fibre and phenolic extract.

Agri-food recycled product	Benchmark product:	More information:	Scale:	Source:	Kg/CO ₂ emissions per kg of product ⁹	Conventional cost (euro/kg)
Fiber from food waste	Inulin from root chicory	Root chicory is defined as an herbaceous plant with a fleshy taproot, and it is the main source of inulin. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre.	Industrial	Hingsamer et al. [83]	1,41	4,9/7
Phenolic extract from food waste	Antioxidant-rich powder extract from beet wastes	Ten different scenarios using beet root and leaf residues as inputs and five different extraction techniques. Used reference is pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) on beet leaves, for 1 g.	Laboratory	Arias et al.[84]	60	Not available
	Antioxidants from olive mill wastewater (OMW)	Three polyphenolic compounds recovered with liquid-liquid solvent extraction (three different solvents tested). Used reference is hydroxytyrosol extraction (0,247 kg from 1 m ³ OMW) with ethyl acetate solvent.	Laboratory	Kalogerakis et al. [85]	13300	Not available

⁹ Data from deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

	Starch aerogel tablets containing vitamin E	Corn-based starch, aerogel preparation using supercritical carbon dioxide impregnation. Used reference the vitamin E (α -tocopherol, TOC) amount (15 mg) in a tablet (120 mg).	Industrial	De Marco et al. [86]	1687	Not available
	C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	Dataset name: "ascorbic acid production", location RER. LCIA results, EF v3.0.	Industrial	ecoinvent 3.8 database	2,9093	9,8
	Quercetin	antioxidant flavonoid present in onions	Industrial	CTNC expert judgement	Not available	28
	Hydroquinone	Organic compound naturally present in some foods and plants	Conventional	ecoinvent 3.10 database	4,7174 ¹⁰	8,3

Source: elaborated by the authors

For this comparison, the environmental costs considered both for the conventional and the A2C product, are limited to the CO₂ equivalent emissions. Since for quercetin no LCA information was available, the comparison is purely based on the conventional cost.

Table 18 and Table 19, as well as Figure 21 and Figure 22, show the results of the comparison.

Table 18 A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – fibre from lemon waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon waste) – default scenario	363,64	1,05	364,69
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon waste) – optimized scenario	140,85	1,05	141,90
Conventional	Inulin from root chicory¹¹	7,44	0,08 ¹²	7,52

Source: elaborated by the authors

¹⁰ Environmental impact data are derived from Ecoinvent 3.10 dataset "Hydroquinone {RER}| hydroquinone production | Cut-off, U"

¹¹ Organic inulin price is currently 7-10€/kg. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre (expert judgement from CTNC).

¹² Only environmental externalities associated to CO₂ equivalent emissions have been included in the calculation.

Figure 21 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Fiber from lemon waste

Source: elaborated by the authors

From the comparison, the cost of the fibre from lemon waste appears still significantly higher than the organic inulin.

Table 19 A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – phenolic extract from lemon waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – default scenario	344,95	3,98	348,93
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – optimized scenario	114,65	3,98	118,63
Conventional	C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	9,8	0,93	10,73
Conventional	Hydroquinone ¹³	8,8	0,77	9,57

Source: elaborated by the authors | n.a =not available

¹³ Hydroquinone/inulin price is currently 7,3-10,3 €/kg (www.pharmacompass.com/price/hydroquinone). It is used as a source of phenolic substances.

Figure 22 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Phenolic extract

Source: elaborated by the authors

With reference to the phenolic extract, the analysis shows that the total eLCC of the phenolic extract is still significantly high in comparison to the conventional product, such as ascorbic acid and Hydroquinone. However, the uncertainty associated with the function of the phenolic extract, due to a wide range of possible final applications, is very high and it affects the overall comparison.

4.2.1.8 Agri-food chain – demo 3: conclusions

The economic life cycle cost (eLCC) assessment for fibres and phenolic extracts from recycled lemon, artichoke, and broccoli waste in Demo 3 reveals that conventional costs dominate, being around 99% of the total costs both for fibre and phenolic extract.

Personnel and maintenance costs are the largest contributors, for fibre, where they account cumulatively for over 80% of expenses. For the phenolic extract the contribution of personnel and maintenance is still highly significant, but lower, being, respectively, 34% and 20%. For the phenolic extract, the cost of the lyophilisation equipment is significant as well, representing 31% of the total conventional cost

The total eLCC per kilogram of fibre ranges from 308,92 € (artichoke) to 364,69 (lemon), while for phenolic extract the value ranges from 348,93 (lemon) to 662,97 (artichoke), reflecting the different output yield, which is waste specific.

Scaling up production significantly reduces costs, with potential savings of 61% for fibre and 66% for phenolic extract. However, the recycled products remain more expensive than conventional alternatives, particularly in comparison to inulin and ascorbic acid or Hydroquinone. With reference to the phenolic extract, however, the uncertainty associated to its function, due to a wide range of possible final applications, is very high and it affects the overall comparison.

4.2.2 Results & conclusions: Agri-food chain – demo 4

The eLCC model has been created on top of the LCA model, in order to assess the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the same input and output included in the LCA model¹⁴. The next figure shows the same detailed flow chart used for the LCA.

Figure 23 DEMO 4 – High added value substances from agri-food residues by green extraction + enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction + microwave.¹⁵

Source: Deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

The following cost categories have been included in the demo:

1. physical input and output conventional costs (raw materials, energy, water, transport, waste management);
2. equipment costs;

¹⁴ For a more detailed description of the LCA model, please consult Deliverable D7.6.

¹⁵ The flow chart is taken from Deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

3. labour costs.

As it was done in the LCA, all the costs have been allocated between the 2 co-products, the fibre (solid phase) and phenolic extract (liquid phase):

- in those processes where both solid and liquid phases are present (pre-treatment and extraction), 75 % of the shared costs are allocated to the solid phase and 25 % to the liquid phase (extraction phase output mass allocation);
- costs related to the centrifugation, ultrafiltration and dehydration phases are entirely allocated to the liquid phase,
- costs related to the MAE and purification&concentration phases are entirely allocated to the solid phase.

The following sections report the life cycle inventories (LCI) of all single processes included in this demo case.

4.2.2.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

As previously reported, the same input/out table used for the LCA has been integrated with the relevant costs, which cover the physical input, such as raw materials, water, energy and transport, as well as the physical output, such as condensed water which is treated as waste. The conventional costs related to each LCA input and output are described in Table 20.

Table 20 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case eLCC

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
agri-food waste (lemon/artichoke)	100	kg	30,00	Inbound transportation cost
water (pre-treatment)	0,205	m3	0,20	
water (for extraction)	0,3	m3	0,29	
water (for MAE)	0,4	m3	0,39	Only for solid phase (phenolic extract)
enzyme	10	ml	10	
citric acid	0,1	kg	3,96	Only used for artichoke waste
Ethanol (for MAE)	120	kg	380,22	Only for solid phase (phenolic extract). 80% of Ethanol is collected to be reused. The input value refers to the net use of ethanol. Ethanol is used to process artichoke waste only
EtOH (for purification)	12,5	kg	39,60	Only for solid phase (phenolic extract – purification phase). 75% of EtOH is collected to be reused. The input value refers to the net use of EtOH. Ethanol is used to process artichoke waste only

Electricity (total)	605,48	kWh	82,06	3 months average cost
<i>Electricity (for waste pre-treatment)</i>	0,28	kWh	0,04	
<i>Electricity (for extraction)</i>	3,0	kWh	0,42	
<i>Electricity (for centrifugation)</i>	20,0	kWh	2,78	Only for liquid phase (dietary fibres)
<i>Electricity (for ultrafiltration)</i>	15,0	kWh	2,08	Only for liquid phase (dietary fibres) – solar energy
<i>Electricity (for dehydration)</i>	48,0	kWh	6,67	Only for liquid phase (dietary fibres)
<i>Electricity (for MAE)</i>	129,2	kWh	17,95	Only for solid phase (phenolic extract)
<i>Electricity (for purification-concentration)</i>	390	kWh	54,20	
Output	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
Discharged water	205	kg	-	The water discarded is treated in the company sewage treatment plan
Discharged water	600	kg	0,19	Waste management cost - Only for solid phase (phenolic extract)
Discharged water	270	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities) - Only for liquid phase (dietary fibres)
Evaporated water	28,8	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities) - Only for liquid phase (dietary fibres)
Solid material from MAE	100	kg	-	This is material sent for demo 5 for processing, therefore no waste cost is considered. Only for solid phase (phenolic extract)
Fiber (product)	1,2	kg	-	Recycling process output
Phenolic extract (product)	0,3	kg	-	Recycling process output

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.2.2 Equipment and installation costs

In order to process the input waste stream, the yearly rental cost of the equipment was considered.

For the extraction phase, the cost of the equipment designed for the demo has been considered, with an expected life of 20 years.

For the centrifugation, ultrafiltration and dehydration of the liquid phase, as well as for the MAE of the solid phase, no new equipment was needed, therefore no installation costs occur.

Finally, for the purification-concentration of the solid phase, the yearly amortization costs have been considered, according to expert judgement from DMC.

Table 21 reports, per each type of equipment, the allocated cost to the recycled co-products.

Table 21 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case LCC – equipment costs

Input	Conventional Cost (Amortization cost per year) (EURO)
Pre-treatment equipment	2760 (cost for renting 1 year)
Extraction equipment	350.000 (cost of the equipment)
Oven (for purification&concentration)	250 (yearly amortization cost of the equipment)
Filtration equipment (for purification&concentration)	3000 (yearly amortization cost of the equipment)

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.2.3 Labour costs

According to expert judgement from DMC, Table 22 reports the personnel cost required to process 100 kg of agrifood waste.

Table 22 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the agrifood demo case LCC – personnel costs

Input	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
Personnel cost (factory worker)	16	20 EUR/h - 8h/ton
Personnel cost (laboratory technician)	200	25 EUR/h - 80h/ton
Personnel cost (laboratory technician)	75	25 EUR/h - 30h/ton

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.2.4 Waste management costs

The food waste recycling process produces wastewater generated in the agrifood waste pre-treatment and in the purification-concentration of the solid phase, that needs to be treated as wastewater. Waste management costs are reported in Table 21. Waste management and wastewater treatment costs related with the solid phase have been entirely allocated to the production of the phenolic extract, while the wastewater treatment cost related with agrifood waste pre-treatment has been proportionally allocated to both co-products. Solid material produced from MAE (solid phase) was not considered as waste since the material is sent for Demo 5 for processing.

4.2.2.5 Agri-food chain-Demo4: total eLCC

The current paragraph reports the results of the whole recycling process of the Demo 4 and their co-products, fibre and phenolic extract, including the associated environmental costs, deriving from the application of the Delft University of Technology to the LCA results, with

the details per cost category and per life cycle phase. As previously reported for demo 3, for the environmental externalities the Environmental Prices method has been applied.

Table 23, Table 24, Table 25 and Figure 24, Figure 25 & Figure 26 show the results of the eLCC assessment of the production of 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon and artichoke waste. From these tables and figures, it is evident that for both co-products, the total eLCC is driven by the conventional cost, which represents at least 98% of the overall costs for all products. Equipment costs are the largest contributors, representing 68% for the fibres (mainly for pre-treatment and extraction), 92% for the phenolic extract from lemon waste and 82% for the phenolic extract from artichoke waste, mainly for MAE process. For the fibre personnel costs represent 24% for the fibres (mainly for extraction), while for the phenolic extract from artichoke, raw material costs (mainly ethanol) represent 11%.

Table 23 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon/artichoke waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection	Recycling process - pre-treatment	Recycling process - extraction	Recycling process - centrifugation	Recycling process - ultrafiltration	Recycling process - dehydration	Waste management	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,00	0,02	0,26	2,32	0,00	5,56	0,00	8,16	1,5%
Equipment cost	0,00	258,68	114,43	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	373,11	68,8%
Personnel cost	0,00	10,00	124,97	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	134,96	24,9%
Raw materials cost	0,00	0,00	8,72	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	8,72	1,6%
Transport cost	12,50	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	12,50	2,3%
Water cost	0,00	0,13	0,19	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,31	0,1%
Waste management cost	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,0%
Total conventional cost	12,50	268,83	248,57	2,32	-	5,56	-	537,76	99,2%
Environmental costs	0,34	0,01	0,24	1,07	0,30	2,57	-	4,53	0,8%
Total eLCC	12,84	268,84	248,81	3,39	0,30	8,13	-	542,29	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 24 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection & pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process - extraction & filtration	Recycling process - purification	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	0,35	59,83	180,66	240,87	2,2%
Equipment cost	344,91	152,57	8139,53	1625,00	10262,01	92,7%
Personnel cost	13,33	166,62	0,00	250,00	429,95	3,9%
Raw materials cost	0,00	11,63	0,00	0,00	11,63	0,1%
Transport cost	16,66	0,00	0,00	0,00	16,66	0,2%
Waste management cost	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,64	0,64	0,0%
Water cost	0,17	0,25	1,32	0,00	1,74	0,0%

Total conventional cost	374,93	331,17	8.199,37	2.056,30	10.961,77	99,0%
Environmental costs	0,47	0,32	27,66	83,80	112,25	1,0%
Total eLCC	375,40	331,49	8.227,03	2.140,10	11.074,01	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 25 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled artichoke waste (Euro)

Cost category	Waste input collection & pre-treatment	Recycling process - general activities	Recycling process – extraction & filtration	Recycling process - purification	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,03	0,35	59,83	180,66	240,87	1,9%
Equipment cost	344,91	152,57	8139,53	1625,00	10262,01	81,6%
Personnel cost	13,33	166,62	0,00	250,00	429,95	3,4%
Raw materials cost	0,00	11,63	1267,43	132,02	1411,08	11,2%
Transport cost	16,66	0,00	0,00	0,00	16,66	0,1%
Waste management cost	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,64	0,64	0,0%
Water cost	0,17	0,25	1,32	0,00	1,74	0,0%
Total conventional cost	374,93	331,17	9.466,79	2.188,32	12.361,22	98,2%
Environmental costs	0,47	0,32	125,41	93,98	220,18	1,8%
Total eLCC	375,40	331,49	9.592,21	2.282,30	12.581,40	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 24 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fibre from lemon/artichoke waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 25 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 26 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Focusing on the conventional costs, Figure 27, Figure 28 & Figure 29 clearly show the % contribution of each type of cost to the total conventional costs (the thickness of the arrow is proportional to its impact). For the fibre, cost from the cutting and homogenizing machine (pre-treatment), represents around 48% of the total conventional costs, while personnel costs bring an additional 25% and the equipment for extraction (microwave) another 21%. For the phenolic extract the microwave equipment for MAE and purification and concentration covers 75% and 67% of the total conventional cost for, respectively, lemon waste and artichoke waste input. For the latter, the weight of ethanol represents around 11% of the total conventional cost.

Figure 27 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of fibre from lemon/artichoke waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 28 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 29 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of phenolic extract from artichoke waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

As for Demo 3, Equipment cost and Personnel cost, are highly influenced by the demo testing small scale, which prevents the recycling process from achieving a high level of efficiency. Therefore, a sensitivity analysis has been conducted to assess how the total cost would change if a higher scale and higher efficiency were applied. According to DMC expert judgment, the current equipment set could allow a total output up to 20 kg per year, treating a double amount of food waste input, in comparison to the default scenario. The increased production can bring scale economy to equipment cost.

Figure 31 and Figure 32, and Table 26, Table 27 show the results of the total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of fibre and 1 kg of phenolic extract from lemon and artichoke waste. From the sensitivity analysis it is evident the considerable cost reduction for both co-products, as the fibre cost is reduced by 34% and the phenolic extract by 34-39%, thanks to a reduction in equipment costs (between -42% and -50%).

Figure 30 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - fibre from lemon/artichoke waste - sensitivity analysis

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 26 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of fibre from recycled lemon/artichoke waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	8,16	8,16	0%
Equipment cost	373,11	186,55	-50%
Personnel cost	134,96	134,96	0%
Raw materials cost	8,72	8,72	0%
Transport cost	12,50	12,50	0%
Water cost	0,31	0,31	0%
Total conventional cost	537,76	351,21	-35%
Environmental costs	4,53	4,53	0%
Total eLCC	542,29	355,74	-34%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 31 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - phenolic extract from lemon waste - sensitivity analysis

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 27 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled lemon waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	240,87	240,87	0%
Equipment cost	10.262,01	5.943,51	-42%
Personnel cost	429,95	429,95	0%
Raw materials cost	11,63	11,63	0%
Transport cost	16,66	16,66	0%
Waste management cost	0,64	0,64	0%
Water cost	1,74	1,74	0%
Total conventional cost	10.963,50	6.645,00	-39%
Environmental costs	112,25	112,25	0%
Total eLCC	11.075,75	6.757,24	-39%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 32 Total eLCC per life cycle phase (EUR/kg) - phenolic extract from artichoke waste - sensitivity analysis

Source: elaborated by the authors

Table 28 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of phenolic extract from recycled artichoke waste (Euro) - sensitivity analysis

Cost category	Default scenario	Alternative scenario	Cost reduction (%)
Energy cost - electricity	240,87	240,87	0%
Equipment cost	10.262,01	5.943,51	-42%
Personnel cost	429,95	429,95	0%
Raw materials cost	1.411,08	1.411,08	0%
Transport cost	16,66	16,66	0%
Waste management cost	0,64	0,64	0%
Water cost	1,74	1,74	0%
Total conventional cost	12.362,95	8.044,45	-35%
Environmental costs	220,18	220,18	0%
Total eLCC	12.583,14	8.264,63	-34%

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.2.6 Agri-food recycled products vs conventional products: demo 4

As it was done for demo 3, this section focuses on a possible comparison of the total eLCC assessment of the fibre and the phenolic extract from recycled food waste, against

conventional (virgin) products that could be considered as alternative products already available.

Since the function of both the fibre and the phenolic extract is not yet fully defined, given that these substances can be included in a wide range of different formulations, the identification of possible benchmark products is still uncertain. For the phenolic extract, which is rich in antioxidant compounds (polyphenols, flavonoids), currently there is no proper reference product, since there is no nutritional claim on polyphenols or antioxidant capacity. In the LCA, some benchmark products have been investigated, as reported in the next table. Unfortunately, the conventional cost was not available for the whole list of products. On the contrary, for quercetin, only the conventional cost was provided Table 29. Moreover, the phenolic extract obtained within A2C project is much richer in concentration than the conventional products: A2C extract has a phenolic concentration which ranges from 50% up to 70%, while the conventional products reach on average only 5%.

Table 29 Potential benchmark products for fibre and phenolic extract.

Agri-food recycled product	Benchmark product:	More information:	Scale:	Source:	Kg/CO ₂ emissions per kg of product ¹⁶	Conventional cost (euro/kg)
Fiber from food waste	Inulin from root chicory	Root chicory is defined as an herbaceous plant with a fleshy taproot, and it is the main source of inulin. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre.	Industrial	Hingsamer et al. [83]	1,41	4,9/7
Phenolic extract from food waste	Antioxidant-rich powder extract from beet wastes	Ten different scenarios using beet root and leaf residues as inputs and five different extraction techniques. Used reference is pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) on beet leaves, for 1 g.	Laboratory	Arias et al.[84]	60	Not available
	Antioxidants from olive mill wastewater (OMW)	Three polyphenolic compounds recovered with liquid-liquid solvent extraction (three different solvents tested). Used reference is hydroxytyrosol extraction (0,247 kg from 1 m ³ OMW) with ethyl acetate solvent.	Laboratory	Kalogerakis et al. [85]	13300	Not available

¹⁶ Data from deliverable D7.6 “Environmental assessment, LCA and A2C circularity monitoring”, Essi Paronen (VTT), Eveliina Hylkilä (VTT), Katri Behm (VTT).

	Starch aerogel tablets containing vitamin E	Corn-based starch, aerogel preparation using supercritical carbon dioxide impregnation. Used reference the vitamin E (α -tocopherol, TOC) amount (15 mg) in a tablet (120 mg).	Industrial	De Marco et al. [86]	1687	Not available
	C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	Dataset name: "ascorbic acid production", location RER. LCIA results, EF v3.0.	Industrial	ecoinvent 3.10 database	2,9093	9,8
	Quercetin	antioxidant flavonoid present in onions	Industrial	CTNC expert judgement	Not available	28
	Hydroquinone	Industrial	Conventional	ecoinvent 3.10 database	4,7174 ¹⁷	8,3

Source: elaborated by the authors

For this comparison, the environmental costs considered both for the conventional and the A2C product, are limited to the CO₂ equivalent emissions. Since for quercetin no LCA information was available, the comparison is purely based on the conventional cost.

Table 30 and Table 31, as well as Figure 33 and Figure 34, show the results of the comparison.

Table 30 A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – fibre from lemon/artichoke waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon/artichoke waste) – default scenario	537,76	4,53	542,29
Recycled (A2C)	Fiber (from lemon/artichoke waste) – optimized scenario	351,21	4,53	355,74
Conventional	Inulin from root chicory ¹⁸	7,44	0,08 ¹⁹	7,52

Source: elaborated by the authors

¹⁷ Environmental impact data are derived from Ecoinvent 3.10 dataset "Hydroquinone {RER}| hydroquinone production | Cut-off, U"

¹⁸ Organic inulin price is currently 7-10€/kg. It is used to enrich products with fibre. It is soluble fibre, and the purity is usually around 80-90% fibre (expert judgement from CTNC).

¹⁹ Only environmental externalities associated to CO₂ equivalent emissions have been included in the calculation.

Figure 33 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Fiber from lemon/artichoke waste

Source: elaborated by the authors

From the comparison, the cost of the fibre from lemon/artichoke waste appears still significantly higher than the organic inulin.

Table 31 A2C products vs conventional systems - total LCC – phenolic extract from lemon and artichoke waste

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – default scenario	10.963,50	112,25	11.075,75
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from lemon waste) – optimized scenario	6.645,00	112,25	6.757,24
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from artichoke waste) – default scenario	12.362,95	220,18	12.583,14
Recycled (A2C)	Phenolic extract (from artichoke waste) – optimized scenario	8.044,45	220,18	8.264,63
Conventional	C-vitamin, ascorbic acid production	9,8	0,93	10,73
Conventional	Hydroquinone ²⁰	8,8	0,77	9,57

Source: elaborated by the authors

²⁰ Hydroquinone price is currently 7,3-10,3 €/kg (www.pharmacompass.com/price/hydroquinone). It is used as a source of phenolic substances.

Figure 34 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Phenolic extract

Source: elaborated by the authors

With reference to the phenolic extract, the analysis shows that the total eLCC of the phenolic extract is still significantly high in comparison to the conventional product, such as ascorbic acid and Hydroquinone. However, the uncertainty associated with the function of the phenolic extract, due to a wide range of possible final applications, is very high and it affects the overall comparison. Moreover, as previously mentioned, the phenolic extract obtained through the A2C project has a significantly higher concentration than conventional products, leading to superior quality.

4.2.2.7 Agri-food chain – demo 4: conclusions

The eLCC assessment for Demo 4 indicates that conventional costs dominate, comprising at least 98% of total costs for fibres and phenolic extracts from lemon and artichoke waste. Equipment costs are the largest contributors, accounting for 68% of fibre production costs (542.29 €/kg) and 92% and 82% of phenolic extract production costs from lemon and artichoke waste, respectively. Personnel costs significantly impact fibre costs (24%), while ethanol usage contributes 11% to artichoke-derived phenolic extract costs. The high cost of the equipment is largely due to MAE being a prototype specifically designed for the A2C project, making it expensive.

The total eLCC for fibres varies from 355,74 €/kg for lemon and 542,29 €/kg for artichoke, while total LCC for phenolic extracts varies from 11,075.75 €/kg for lemon and 12,583.14

€/kg for artichoke waste. Scaling up production could reduce costs by 34-39%, but recycled products remain significantly more expensive than conventional alternatives. However, the phenolic extract produced through the A2C project has a significantly higher concentration than conventional products—up to 70% compared to just 5%—resulting in superior quality.

4.2.3 Results and conclusions. Plastic chain

As it was performed in the LCA (see Deliverable D7.6) an eLCC assessment has been conducted on the plastic chain case study, which is focused on upcycle plastic residues from the food sector to high added value products. The demo consists of recycling agricultural mulch film waste and waste from aseptic bags produced by the food industry, into new plastic pellet, which can substitute conventional LDPE virgin pellet, currently available on the market.

The eLCC model has been created on top of the LCA model, in order to assess the conventional and environmental externality costs related to the same input and output included in the LCA model²¹.

The comparison encompasses two types of pellets:

- a. Pellet blend which is 1/3 by weight made of the recycled LDPE and virgin calcium carbonate manufactured in the A2C project (hereafter referred to as A2C pellet) and 2/3 virgin LDPE pellet;
- b. 100 % virgin LDPE pellet (conventional product).

The following cost categories have been included in the demo:

1. physical input and output conventional costs (raw materials, energy, water, transport, waste management);
2. equipment costs;
3. installation costs;
4. labour costs;
5. maintenance costs.

The following sections report the life cycle inventories (LCI) of all single processes included in this demo case.

²¹ For a more detailed description of the LCA model, please consult Deliverable D7.6.

4.2.3.1 Physical input and output conventional costs

As previously reported, the same input/out table used for the LCA has been integrated with the relevant costs, which cover the physical input, such as raw materials, water, energy and transport, as well as the physical output, such as soil and plastic sawdust which are treated as waste.

The conventional costs related to each LCA input and output are described in Figure 30.

Table 32 Used life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic chain demo case eLCC

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
agricultural mulch film waste	1735	kg	173,5	
aluminium waste	10	kg	1	
Demo 1 output	140	kg	14	
calcium carbonate	30	kg	3,15	
polyelectrolyte chemical for water treatment	0,54	kg	3,07	
calcium oxide	6,70	kg	1,59	
water	362,45	kg	1,25	
electricity	1090,51	kWh	174,48	
electricity from solar panel	100,89	kWh	0	
diesel	1,93	kg	2,38	
Transport (agricultural mulch film waste)	1735 x 60	kgkm	22,55	
Transport (calcium carbonate)	30 x 120	kgkm	transport cost included in raw material cost	
Transport (polyelectrolyte)	1,79E-04 x 150	kgkm	transport cost included in raw material cost	
Transport (calcium oxide)	6,70 x 150	kgkm	transport cost included in raw material cost	
Transport (diesel)	1,93 x 50	kgkm	transport cost included in raw material cost	
Output	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
soil	671,35	kg	159,11	Waste management cost
plastic sawdust	239,83	kg	13,76	Waste management cost
filter chunk	3,59	kg	0,21	Waste management cost
Transport (soil)	671 x 35	kgkm	transport cost included in waste management cost	
Transport (plastic sawdust)	0,08 x 94	kgkm	transport cost included in waste management cost	
Transport (filter chunk)	3,59 x 94	kgkm	transport cost included in waste management cost	

Input	Amount	Unit	Conventional Cost (EURO)	Comment
carbon dioxide to air	6,10	kg	-	No conventional costs attached (only environmental externalities)
A2C pellet	1000	kg	-	Recycling process output

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.3.2 Equipment and installation costs

In order to process the input waste stream, 2 types of equipment are needed: a washing plant and an extruder, which are fully dedicated to the recycling process. Equipment costs include the installation costs as well as the yearly amortization cost which has been calculated considering a yearly production based on 17.721,78 kg of input waste and 10 years life span (Table 33).

Table 33 Equipment life cycle inventory (LCI) data in the plastic film demo case eLCC

Input	Conventional Cost for the whole production/recycling process (Amortization cost per year ²²) (EURO)
Washing plant	40500
Extruder	28700

Source: elaborated by the authors

4.2.3.3 Labour costs

According to expert judgement from GWC plastics, to get 1 t of recycled pellet (for cleaning/decontamination and recycling, i.e. the whole process), it takes about 1,5 hours, with an hourly cost of 86,63 €/h.

4.2.3.4 Maintenance costs

Total yearly maintenance costs, for the equipment reported in the use in the process, sum up to 131.508 € per year, with a yearly production based on 17.721,78 kg of input waste.

²² Amortization has been calculated over 10 years of use of each equipment.

4.2.3.5 Waste management costs

The agricultural film waste recycling process produces soil, as solid waste, and plastic sawdust, that needs to be treated as wastewater. Waste management cost therefore includes the cost of the treatment of both waste streams, as already reported in Table 32.

4.2.3.6 Plastic chain: total eLCC

The current paragraph reports the results of the whole recycling process and its product, the recycled pellet, including the associated environmental costs, deriving from the application of the Delft University of Technology to the LCA results, with the details per cost category and per life cycle phase.

Table 34 and Figure 35 and Figure 36 show the results of the eLCC assessment of the production of 1 kg of recycled plastic pellet from recycled agricultural mulch film waste. It appears clearly that the total eLCC is driven by the conventional cost, which represents around 91% of the overall costs, whereas raw material cost, as waste input collection, is the largest contributor, followed by electricity and personnel cost.

Table 34 Total eLCC for the production of 1 kg of recycled plastic pellet from recycled agricultural mulch film waste (Euro)

Cost category	Total Cost	% on total
Energy cost - electricity	0,17	26,0%
Energy cost - thermal energy	0,00	0,4%
Equipment cost	0,02	3,2%
Maintenance cost	0,04	6,2%
Personnel cost	0,13	19,2%
Raw materials cost	0,20	29,3%
Transport cost	0,02	3,7%
Waste management cost	0,02	3,0%
Water cost	0,00	0,2%
Total conventional cost	0,61	91,0%
Environmental costs	0,06	9,0%
Total eLCC	0,67	100%

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 35 Total eLCC assessment for 1 kg of recycled pellet from agricultural film waste (EURO/kg)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Focusing on the conventional costs, Figure 36 clearly shows the % contribution of each type of cost to the total conventional costs (the thickness of the arrow is proportional to its impact). Maintenance represents about 45% of the total conventional costs, while equipment as a whole brings an additional 23%, and waste management cost, mainly to treat soil waste, is about 20%.

Figure 36 Total conventional cost breakdown for 1 kg of recycled pellet from agricultural film waste (%)

Source: elaborated by the authors

Since equipment cost, and partly maintenance, are influenced by the demo testing small scale, which prevents the recycling process from achieving high level of efficiency, the overall eLCC cost of the recycled plastic pellet would certainly be reduced with a higher scale of yearly production.

4.2.3.7 Plastic-film recycled products vs conventional products.

This section focuses on a possible comparison of the total eLCC assessment of the recycled pellet from agricultural film waste against the conventional (virgin) pellet that could be considered as an alternative product already available. Since the final product is a pellet which is a mix of 1/3 of A2C recycled plastic pellet and 2/3 of virgin LDPE pellet, an additional conventional cost of 1,5 euro per kg has been attached to the virgin LDPE pellet, according to expert judgement from GWC Plastic.

The following tables and figures Table 35 and Figure 37 show the results of the comparison.

Table 35 A2C recycled product vs conventional product - total LCC – plastic pellet

Type of product	Product	Conventional LCC	Environmental cost	Total eLCC
Recycled (A2C)	Plastic pellet (33% recycled content)	1,20	0,28	1,48
Conventional	Plastic pellet (100% virgin content)	1,5	0,39	1,89

Source: elaborated by the authors

Figure 37 A2C product vs conventional product – total eLCC – Plastic pellet

Source: elaborated by the authors

From the comparison, both environmental externalities costs and the conventional cost for the recycled pellet are lower than the virgin pellet ones. Therefore the total eLCC of the 33% recycled pellet is 21% lower than the 100% virgin pellet.

4.3 SO-LCA territorial systemic solution

This section presents the results of the social organisational evaluation (micro-level evaluation). These are framed under deliverable *D.7.5. Evaluation framework and methodology* and follow the procedure of the results presented in the deliverable submitted in March 2023 *D7.8. Socioeconomic and sociocultural analysis report (Draft)*. Therefore, to avoid repetition and for the sake of simplicity, the methodological information used in the screening phase is presented in D.7.8. and updated (when necessary) in the next sections of this deliverable (D.7.9).

4.3.1 Goal & scope

The social evaluation is based on the **Social-Organisational Life Cycle Assessment (SO-LCA)**. This approach is grounded on the key role of organisations in the transition towards sustainability and CE [12]. Therefore, the selected **unit of analysis** has been the organisation. As in the screening stage, the **goal** of this study (SO-LCA) is to analyse the performance of the organisations in order to promote the improvement of social conditions and/or their contribution to the social development of each organisations' stakeholders. The selected organisations belong to both value chains (Agrifood and Plastic), but in this occasion are grouped by type of organisation (see section 4.1 Methodology) and the groups are presented in the following table: Table 36 SO-LCA groups of entities analysed **Error! Reference source not found..**

Table 36 SO-LCA groups of entities analysed

	Private for-profit organisations	Research Organisations	Other (Civil Society Organisations- CSO)
<i>Murcia (Spain)</i>	CITROMIL, GWC, SOLPLAST, MCTS, CETECBIO	CTNC, CETEC	PRIMAFRIO, PROEXPORT
<i>Granada (Spain)</i>	DMC		
<i>Catalunya (Spain)</i>	IRIS		
<i>Reference year</i>	2023	2023	2023

Source: elaborated by the authors

The SO-LCA is carried out by type of organisation in an aggregated way, not considering the organisations individually. Also, the results must be considered carefully due to the heterogeneity of the organisations (different number of employees, activities...). In the group of private for-profit organisations, the majority of the organisations belong to the agrifood Value Chain (VC) (CITROMIL, DMC, MCTS, CETECBIO). In this group, there are two entities based outside of the region of Murcia: DMC and IRIS. Moreover, 43% of the entities are SMEs. The average number of employees is 70,7, ranging from 203 to 3. Regarding the Research organisations group, both institutions (CTNC and CETEC) are based in the region of Murcia. CTNC operates in both the agrifood and the plastic value chains whereas CETEC only in the plastic one. The average number of employees is 25. The last group, named other, is composed of a foundation (PRIMAFRIO), operating in the agrifood VC, and an association (PROEXPORT), operating in the plastic value chain. The average number of employees is 4,5.

The reporting organisation was chosen as the **unit of analysis** by setting the **boundaries of the system** “*from cradle to gate*”, in accordance with the UNEP guidelines for SO-LCA [13].

The SO-LCA calls upon a stakeholder approach where the potential impacts on different stakeholder categories are considered. The quality of an organisation’s relationships and engagement with its stakeholders is critical for its social performance. As in the screening exercise, the **stakeholders’ categories** included in the UNEP guidelines are considered as well as several of their corresponding impact subcategories (see 4.3.2. Inventory and procedure methodology). Specifically, the selected stakeholders’ categories are workers, value chain actors, society, local community and consumers. The category “children” has been excluded due to its irrelevance with respect to the sectorial dimensions of the organisations under assessment.

4.3.2 Inventory and procedure methodology

The criteria to choose the metrics was the same followed in the screening stage (D.7.8.). The indicators are mainly based on the UNEP guidelines and on the results of fuzzy Delphi²³

²³ This method combines Delphi method and fuzzy theory analysis to achieve a consensus by solving the vagueness and ambiguity of expert judgments to improve the efficiency and quality of traditional Delphi method

study carried out by A. Padilla-Rivera, B.B.T. do Carmo, G. Arcese et al [14]. Bibliographic research was also conducted to review the most recent articles related with the selection of SO-LCA indicators [15], [16]. Thus, the metrics that meet the methodological requirements set in the evaluation framework (relevance, measurability, reliability, timeliness, comparability, clarity and availability) have been chosen, correlated with the stakeholders and the *social impact categories*. Moreover, and following the UNEP guidelines for SO-LCA and the scholars' proposals, site specific indicators were associated with the impact subcategories and Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) as shown in the following table:

Table 37 List of stakeholder categories, impact subcategories, indicators and SDGs

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	Indicators	Related SDGs
WORKERS	Forced labour	- Employment terms (WQ1) - Forced Labour (W1)	SDG 3 SDG 8 SDG 10
	Fair salary	- Minimum wage, per month (W3) - Organisation average wage, per month (W4)	SDG 1 SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 4
	Working hours	- Flexibility (WQ2) - Full-time staff (W5)	SDG 3 SDG 8
	Equal opportunities/ discrimination	- Gender equality (W6) - Equal opportunities policies (W7)	SDG 1 SDG 4 SDG 5 SDG 8 SDG 10
	Health and Safety	- Occupational safety measures (WQ3) - Lost time injury frequency rate (W8) - Presence of sufficient safety measures (W9)	SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 6 SDG 8
	Social benefits, legal issues	- Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations (W10.1 – W10.2)	SDG 3 SDG 8 SDG 9 SDG 11
	Workers' rights	- Trade unions density (WQ4) - Collective Bargaining Agreement (W11.1, W11.2, W11.3, W11.4)	SDG 8 SDG 10 SDG 16
	Sexual harassment	- Sexual harassment incidents reported (W12)	SDG 8
VALUE CHAIN ACTORS	Fair competition	- Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour (VC1.1- VC1.2)	SDG 12
	Promoting social responsibility	- Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (VC2) - Suppliers audit (VC3)	SDG 12
	Supplier relationships	- Suppliers' communication relationship (VC4)	SDG 12

surveys through fuzzy set theory, which addresses situations in which humans cannot precisely describe a judgement.

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	Indicators	Related SDGs
	Respect of intellectual property rights	- Use of local intellectual property (VC5)	SDG 9
	Wealth distribution	- Fair price definition (VC6)	SDG 1 SDG 8 SDG 10
SOCIETY	Public commitment to sustainability issues	- Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues (S1)	SDG 12 SDG 17
	Contribution to economic development	- Total taxation per capita (S2)	SDG 1 SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 4 SDG 8 SDG 9
	Technology development	- Technology transfer (S3) - Investments in technology development/transfer (S4)	SDG 4 SDG 9 SDG 17
	Corruption	- Corruption (S5)	SDG 16
	Poverty alleviation	- Poverty alleviation programme (S6)	SDG 1 SDG 2
LOCAL COMMUNITY	Access to material resources	- Environmental management system (LC1)	SDG 9 SDG 12
	Access to immaterial resources	- Community education initiatives (LC2)	SDG 4 SDG 12
	Delocalization and migration	- Immigrant workforce rate (LC3) - Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community (LC4)	SDG 9 SDG 10 SDG 11
	Cultural heritage	- Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage (LC5)	SDG 11
	Safe and healthy living conditions	- Promotion of community health (LC6)	SDG 3 SDG 6
	Community engagement	- Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation (LC7) - Number of meetings with community stakeholders (LC8) - Organisational support (volunteer-hours or financial) for community initiatives (LC9)	SDG 11 SDG 12
	Local employment	- Workforce hired locally (LC10) - Spending on locally based suppliers (LC11)	SDG 8

Stakeholder category	Impact subcategory	Indicators	Related SDGs
	Secure living conditions	- Security complaints by the community (LC12)	SDG 3 SDG 16
CONSUMERS	Health and Safety	- Labelling (C1) - Consumer complaints (C2) - Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System (C3)	SDG 2 SDG 3 SDG 12
	Feedback mechanism	- Presence of consumers feedback mechanism (C4)	SDG 12
	Consumer privacy	- Consumers complaints related to breach of privacy (C5)	SDG 8 SDG 16
	Transparency	- Organisation communication transparency (C6)	SDG 9 SDG 12
	End-of-life	- Internal management systems (C7)	SDG 12 SDG

4.3.3 Data gathering tools and process

The tools used in this stage were designed²⁴ during the preliminary screening phase and were also applied in the final project assessment. Two main questionnaires were utilised: the **Project Manager Form** and the **Workers' Questionnaire**. The former was targeted at senior management positions within the selected organisations, focusing exclusively on questions related to the SO-LCA. The Workers' Questionnaire, on the other hand, served a dual purpose: it gathered information to enrich the conclusions related to the *Workers stakeholder category* and included questions about awareness, desire, and CE consciousness. This provided an initial understanding of the perceptions of employees within the A2C organisations and contributed with valuable insights to the conclusions of the macro-level evaluation. This approach ensured a comprehensive data collection process, addressing both organisational and employee-level perspectives effectively.

Slight changes were made in the workers questionnaire to make it more straightforward. Questions about electronic devices and smartphone applications were removed from the CE awareness section since, after the screening, it was observed that they were out of scope and did not provide any relevant information for the study. Thus, the final picture of the workers questionnaire is as follows:

- Sociodemographic section, made up of 5 questions;
- SO-LCA section, made up of 4 questions;

²⁴ For more information regarding the questionnaires design see section 8.3.1. of D.7.8.

- New Ecological Paradigm section, made up of 1 question;
- Survey on consumers- awareness section, made up of 3 questions;
- Survey on consumers-desire section, made up of 2 questions;
- Circular economy awareness section, made up of 5 questions (6 question-items were removed).

For further details on the indicators please see D.7.8., annex 14.1. Social Indicators Battery. Regarding the data gathering process, it was built upon the process followed on the screening assessment. The partners were contacted through email.

4.3.4 Results per stakeholder category

The main results per stakeholder category of the final evaluation are presented below. As shown in Table 36, even though the organisations are grouped by type, making comparisons between them is impossible. The heterogeneity of organisations makes comparisons difficult, and the results obtained from this exercise can lead to mistakes in the conclusions. Thus, this section aims to set out the main SO-LCA results of the three groups of organisations, comparing the results, where possible, according to national standards, but never between groups or organisations themselves.

Methodological notes:

- In general terms, information has been processed on an aggregated basis per type of organisation. Individual results are shown only when the data reflects something different from the rest of the organisations in the group.
- The size of the first group compared to the other two groups are very different. Thus, comparisons must be done carefully to avoid misinterpretations.
- Although the project has a regional scope, the references used in this case are national. The reason for this decision is that, among the groups of organisations, there are organisations that operate outside the geographical boundaries of the region of Murcia. It was considered then that comparisons with regional specific references in this situation is not rigorous due to the socio-economic heterogeneity between regions in Spain.
- One organisation did not respond to the workers' questionnaire. Indicators WQ1 do not gather all entities' impressions.

4.3.4.1 Stakeholder category: workers

The table below shows the comparison between the organisations involved in A2C and the reference for comparison.

Table 38 Workers: results and references for comparison

Impact Subcategory	Indicators	Group1: Private for-profit organisations	Group2: Research Organisations	Group3: Other (CSO)	Reference
Forced Labour	Employment terms (WQ1)	89%	93%	80%	n.d.
	Forced Labour (W1)	0%	0%	0%	514 [17]
Fair salary	Organisation average wage, per month (W4)	1.875,10€	2.172,28 €	2.363,50 €	2.050,23 € [18]
Working hours	Flexibility (WQ2)	(6/6) 30%	(6/6) 29%	(6/6) 50%	ES:42% [19] - 0.05 (adjustment [20]) ≈37%
	Full-time staff (W5)	97%	96%	22%	88%[21]
Equal opportunities/discrimination	Gender equality (W6)	18%	56%	78%	45.32%[22] Agric: 14% [23]
	Equal opportunities policies (W7)	100%	100%	0%	≈60%[24]
Health and safety	Occupational safety measures (WQ3). Perception.	88%	93%	100%	Mandatory: RD31/1995 ²⁵ and RD39/1997 ²⁶ AGRI SPAIN: incident rates of death 59.36% higher than in other sectors [25]
	Lost time injury frequency rate (W8)	1 (0.35%)	43 (≈7.8%)	0	3,9-37,9 (%TAR) [26]; N=2959 (2024) [27]
	Presence of sufficient safety measures (W9)	100%	100%	100%	RD31/1995 and RD39/1997
Social benefits, legal issues	Evidence of violations of laws and employment regulations (W10.1 – W10.2)	0	0	0	8000€/day (sanctions (€) in MU) [28]. ES 2022: 3520 Sanctions (total) [29, p. 63]
Workers' rights	Trade unions density (WQ4)	9%	7%	0%	12.57%[30]
	Collective Bargaining Agreement (W11.1, W11.2, W11.3, W11.4)	100%	50% ²⁷	0%	Agric 3 CBA (2023); 29290 workers [31]
Sexual harassment	Sexual harassment incidents reported (W12)	0	0	0	810 [29]

Source: elaborated by the authors

Forced labour

²⁵ RD31/1995 - *Prevención de Riesgos Laborales*

²⁶ RD39/1997 - *Reglamento de los Servicios de Prevención*

²⁷ One of the organisations – CBA - is under investigation due to a legal complaint.

The aim of this impact subcategory is to assess the use of forced labour in the organisations. ILO defines forced labour as labour that is undertaken involuntarily and extracted under threat or coercion [32]. None of the organisations reported to have forced workers on their staff (W1). Linked to this impact subcategory, the organisations' employees were asked if they *agreed freely on the employment terms* (WQ1). In all the organisations (*in the three groups*) that were studied, more than 80% of employees reported that they had voluntarily accepted the terms and conditions of their employment, including aspects such as salary, working hours, holiday entitlement, and the terms of resignation. In total, out of 72 respondents, just 7 stated that they did not freely accept the employment terms.

Fair salary

Efforts to ensure Fair Salary and Living Wage are vital for achieving multiple Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). They directly support SDG 1 (ending poverty) and SDG 10 (reducing income inequality), as increasing the income of the lowest earners is essential to narrowing inequality gaps. Additionally, they contribute to SDG 8 (promoting inclusive economic growth and decent work), as improved wages are crucial for achieving these objectives. [33]. This impact subcategory evaluates whether wage practices comply with legal standards, meet or exceed industry averages, and qualify as a living wage. On the one hand, as it is shown in Table 39, Group1 fell short of providing a living wage on average, though they comply with minimum wage laws. On the other hand, Group2 and Group3 generally exceed the living wage, with Group3 providing the highest earnings²⁸.

Table 39 Living, minimum & average wage

	Spain living wage (W2)	Spain minimum wage (W3)	Average wage per month (W4) Group1	Average wage per month (W4) Group2	Average wage per month (W4) Group3
2023	2.050,23 €	1.080 €[34]	1.875,10€	2.172,28 €	2.363,50 €

The data highlights disparities in wage levels across different organisational types and their alignment with living and minimum wage reference.

Working hours

²⁸ It needs to be highlighted that just one organisation out of two provided the organisation average wage in nominal terms, per month. Thus, this result should be considered with caution.

The indicators chosen within this subcategory are “*Flexibility (WQ2)*” and “*Full time staff (W5)*” in order to verify if the number of hours effectively worked was in accordance with the national standards. It addresses excessive working time that hinders a sustainable work-life balance as well as too little working hours limiting a satisfying professional life. According to the workers survey, 30% of workers in Group1 are very satisfied with the job flexibility. Half of the workers are very satisfied in Group3 and the group with the smallest percentage of very satisfied workers is Group2 (29%).

The biggest difference between full-time and part-time employment is the number of hours worked per week. Full-time employees work around 30 to 40 hours a week, while part-time employees typically work less than 30 hours a week. The majority of the A2C organisations workforce are hired full-time. The only group that does not follow this trend is Group3. Jobs in associations and foundations tend to be more temporary due to their reliance on project-based funding, limited budgets, flexible structures, and the short-term nature of their activities.

Equal opportunities/ discrimination

Discrimination is defined as any distinction, exclusion or preference on the basis of race, colour, sex, religion, political opinion, national extraction or social origin, which has the effect of nullifying or impairing equality of opportunity or treatment in employment or occupation (ILO [32]). The subcategory “equal opportunities/ discrimination” aims to assess equal opportunity management practices and the presence of discrimination in the opportunities offered to the workers by the organisations. In Group2 (56%) and 3 (78%) *the percentage of women (W6) as employees* is above the reference figure (45,32%) whereas for Group1, the percentage is significantly lower (18%). Regarding the *presence of equal opportunity policies (W7)*, in Group1 and 2 all the organisations have declared to have formal policies on equal opportunities such as a Gender Equality Plan (GEP). The only Group where none of the organisations have declared to have this type of polices is Group3. This might be due to the type of organisation since not all are forced to have developed a GEP. According to the Spanish law, just those companies with more than 50 workers must have one.

Health and safety

Occupational safety and health (OSH) aim at fostering a safe work environment, where risks to workers health and safety are minimised and the system is well-managed. This means that the employer must not only comply with local OSH legislation but should also strive to

have the best possible OSH system within its means. All workers have the right to a safe and healthy workplace, with the “health and safety” subcategory the perception by workers of *adequate occupational safety measures (WQ3)*, the *lost time injury frequency rate (W8)* and the *presence of sufficient safety measures (W9)* are assessed for the selected organisations.

While all groups comply with regulations, perceptions of safety measures vary, with Group3 reporting the highest satisfaction (100%) and Group1 the lowest (88%). Moreover, Group2 experienced a significantly higher injury rate (7,8%) compared to Group1 (0,35%) and 3 (0%), indicating a potential gap in safety implementation or risk management. Regarding the *W8*²⁹ indicator, although all groups report 100% compliance with sufficient safety measures, the higher injury frequency in Group2 suggests a need for improved enforcement or adaptation of safety protocols.

The agricultural sector is highlighted as particularly high-risk, with fatality rates 59,36% above those in other sectors, underscoring the importance of targeted safety measures in this field.

Social benefits, legal issues

Violations of labour laws by the employer are a threat to well-being and therefore have a potential social impact. In this subcategory we assessed whether organisations comply with current regulations in terms of employment. All the organisations assessed reported that they have not been sanctioned (*W10.1-W10.2*)³⁰ during the last account period (2023) due to non-compliance with the current legislation.

Workers' rights

Freedom of association is the right of all workers and employers to establish and join organisations of their own choosing without previous authorization. Workers should be adequately protected against acts of anti-union discrimination. In A2C, the “workers' rights” subcategory is measured by the indicator “*collective agreement*” (*W11.1, W11.2, W11.3, W11.4*) which is made up of several measurements and by the indicator “*trade unions density*” (*WQ4*).

The analysis reveals significant disparities in workers' rights and representation across different organisational types in relation to trade union density and the implementation of

²⁹W8 indicator: Lost time injury frequency rate

³⁰W10.1-W10.2 indicator: Evidence of violations of law and employment regulations, Number of evidences

Collective Bargaining Agreements (CBAs). Trade union density remains low across all groups, with private for-profit organisations (Group1) at 9%, research organisations (Group2) at 7%, and no union representation in "Other" organisations (Group3). These figures fall short of the national reference of 12.57%, highlighting a general lack of worker organisation and advocacy, particularly in Group3.

Regarding CBAs, Group1 show the highest level of engagement, with 100% having active agreements. Among these, all ensure that workers have access to the agreements and meeting minutes, 43% have union delegates with adequate support for their activities, and all involve union representatives in decision-making processes affecting working conditions. However, only 66%³¹ of these organisations provide a neutral, binding, and independent dispute resolution mechanism. In Group2, 50% report having CBAs, with full compliance in supporting union representation and involving them in decision-making. Nevertheless, none of these organisations offer access to independent dispute resolution processes. For Group3, the lack of CBAs and union representation highlights a gap in worker protection and may be linked to the nature of the organisations.

Overall, the findings highlight the need to address gaps in worker representation and rights, particularly in Group3 and in providing neutral dispute resolution mechanisms. While Group1 and Group2 have made progress in implementing CBAs and supporting union representation, further efforts are necessary to ensure comprehensive and equitable worker protections across all sectors.

Sexual harassment

According to the ILO sexual harassment are unwelcome comments about the workers' appearance; sexual jokes or innuendo; sexual advances or requests for sexual favours; and other verbal or physical conduct eluding to sex including insisting looks. A world of work, free from sexual harassment has become an explicit goal for ILO member states. Within our study, the impact subcategory "sexual harassment" was measured by the indicator "*sexual harassment incidents reported*" (W12) as a means of verification of whether the company registers or not the number of this type of incidents. No such incidents were reported by either organisation assessed.

³¹ This calculation has been made taking into account only six out of the seven organisations.

4.3.4.2 Stakeholder category: value chain actors

The value chain actors showed the following results:

Table 40 Value chain actors: results and references for comparison

Impact Subcategory	Indicators	Group1: Private for-profit organisations	Group2: Research Organisations	Group3: Other (CSO)	Reference
Fair competition	Sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour (VC1.1- VC1.2)	0	0	0	4(MU); 87 (ES) [35]
Promoting social responsibility	Promotion of Corporate Social Responsibility (VC2)	57%	0%	50%	41% [36]
	Suppliers audit (VC3)	(3/6) 69,9%	(1/2) 12,8%	0%	29% (ES) ; ISO 14001: (ES 2018) >26000 orgs. ; total (ES 2014) 2413 [37], [38], [39]
Supplier relationship	Suppliers' communication relationship (VC4)	5	5	5	n.d.
Respect of intellectual property rights	Use of local intellectual property (VC5)	0	0	0	307 (ES 2019 Software licences) [40] ³²
Wealth	Fair price definition (VC6)	29%	50%	0%	n.d.

Source: elaborated by the authors

Fair competition

Fair competition was measured by analysing the sanctions for anti-competitive behaviour: specific items to evaluate this subcategory were *VC1.1 Has your institution been sanctioned for unfair competition (anti-competitive behaviour)?* And *VC1.2 If yes, please indicate the number of sanctions in the last accounting year.*

Among the entities analysed, none of them was sanctioned during the past year. Comparing the regional and national situation, 4 sanctions occurred in Murcia and 87 in Spain in the same period [35].

Promoting social responsibility

Social responsibility (SR) is an organisation's obligation to consider the interests of their stakeholders as customers, employees, shareholders, or communities. By integrating SR into core business processes and stakeholder management, organisations can achieve the ultimate goal of creating both social and corporate value [41]. The promotion of SR was

³² Non comparable

evaluated through the Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) implementation and the audits conducted to suppliers.

Items concerning CSR were VC2 *Does your institution have a Corporate Social Responsibility agreement?* (and also related to suppliers’ relationship), {VC3.1} *Number of hired suppliers audited with regard to social responsibility in the last accounting year.* Most specifically, the relationship with suppliers was evaluated through {VC3.2} *Number of hired suppliers in the last accounting year* and I3-VC4 *Please, indicate how you would rate the relationship with the organisation suppliers.*

Firstly, in absolute terms, 980 suppliers were contracted whilst 536 were actively audited. Secondly, when asking about the number of hired suppliers after audition and/or homologation {VC3.1}, 3 of 6 Group1 organisations declared to conduct audits: just 1 of these 3 audited all providers. Just one of the Group2 organisations audited the suppliers in terms of social responsibility {VC3.1}, not applying for the 100% (14,28% of providers).

Figure 38 Reference analysis and maximum and minimum values in the value chain

Supplier relationship

Supplier relationships are defined as affiliations with organisations that supply another organisation with goods and services. The supplier relationships also concern all mutual activities, co-operations, agreements that regulate the exchanges, trade, and relation among organisations, bearing in mind that every organisation in the value chain is responsible for complying with applicable laws and regulations [41]. In order to assess the organisations’ relationship with their suppliers, they were asked to rate on a scale of 1 (coercive communication) to 6 (very fluent communication) their *communication with this group of actors (VC4)*. In the three groups the communication was rated, on average, with a 5 out of 6, indicating a perception of good communication with suppliers.

Respect of intellectual property rights

Within the impact subcategory “respect of intellectual property rights” the organisations were asked to report the *number of conflicts that arose due to the use of local intellectual property*

(VC5). The reported conflicts have been 0 (in the three groups of organisations) during the last accounting year.

Wealth distribution

The indicator evaluating this impact subcategory was *VC6 Does the organisation have a specific policy for deciding a fair price (i.e., a price that covers all the production costs and returns an acceptable profit margin)?*. It might be assumed that all private for-profit organisations with CSR certifications are subject to fair price procedures, bilaterally. At regional level, less than ≈1% [42] of companies are accredited in CSR (e.g., BCorp). However, given the fact that certifications vs fair price definition are not directly comparable dimensions, a reference point has not been fixed for this indicator (the item asks for gross margin matter, thus subject to uncertainty and organisations' operations and research activities). In the groups of A2C organisations surveyed, there are some entities that have a policy for determining a fair price. In the case of Group 1, this represents 29% of the organisations, while in Group 2 this percentage rises to 50%.

4.3.4.3 Stakeholder category: society

The society stakeholder category showed the following results:

Table 41 Society: results and references for comparison

Impact Subcategory	Indicators	Group1: Private for-profit organisations	Group2: Research Organisations	Group3: Other (CSO)	Reference
Public commitment to sustainability issues	Presence of publicly available documents as promises or agreements on sustainability issues (S1)	71%	0%	50%	29,70% [36]
Contribution to economic development	Total taxation per capita (S2)	3.990.159,03 €	467.071,30€	86.642,07€	159.561 (mill.€) [43] ³³
Technology development	Technology transfer (S3)	29%	50%	50%	13,46% (Total; 753/5594companies) [44], [45]
	Investments in technology development/ transfer (S4)	42%	78%	0%	6% (R&D; n=277 int; n=68 ext) [45]
Corruption	Corruption (S5)	57%	50%	50%	% of companies with a code of conduct: 84%

³³ Non comparable

					n=138 Companies (MU) [D7.8]
Poverty alleviation	Poverty alleviation programme (S6)	14%	50%	50%	MU: 8% (IMV) [46]; Social services outreach: n=3211 [44] ³⁴

Source: elaborated by the authors

Public commitment to sustainability issues

A public commitment is a promise or agreement made by an organisation, or a group of organisations, to its customers, employees, shareholders, local community, or the general public whose fulfilment can be evidenced in a transparent and open way [41]. Typically, this will take the form of performance improvement targets with defined dates for achievement and public reporting of progress. The item *S1 Does the organisation have any public available document as promises or agreements on sustainability issues?* received 5 positive answers (35,7%; N=14 entities) being for-profit (Group1) and civil society organisations (Other – Group3) the most represented.

Table 42 S1 indicator results per Group

Activity	S1 Does the organisation have any public available document as promises or agreements on sustainability issues?	
	Yes (counts, n)	
Group3. Other	1	
Group1. Private for-profit entities	5	
Group2. Research Organisations	1	

Source: elaborated by the authors

Contribution to economic development

This subcategory assesses to what extent the organisation contributes to the economic development of the society [41]. It can be measured at different geographical levels. In this case it is measured by the indicator *“Total taxation per capita” (S2): Indicate in euros the total amount of taxes (all the paid taxes including VAT, social security contributions, Tax on Economic Activities, Corporate income tax, IRPF) paid in the last accounting year.*

The total taxation per capita (S2) in Group1 were 3.990.159,03€ ± 8.517.974,69€ (Min: 60000,03€; Max: 21.353.000,00€). In Group2, S2 were 467.071,30€ ± 18.283,94€ (Min: 454.142,60 €; Max: 480.000,00€). Finally, in Group3 the total taxation per capita (S2) were 86.642,07€ ± 120.844,48 € (Min: 1.192,12€; Max: 172,092,02€).

³⁴ Non comparable

Thus, corporate taxes reveal an important heterogeneity between the cases concerning its size and purchasing-supplying and negotiation power. When compared to the national reference of €159,561 million, the contributions of these specific organisations represent a small fraction of the overall tax revenue. However, their role within their respective sectors is crucial for sustaining employment, funding public services, and supporting economic development initiatives. The disparities in tax contributions also reflect the structural differences in revenue streams, legal tax obligations, and the economic scale of these organisations.

Technology development

Concerning technology development and transfer, our analysis revealed that 5 organisations have technology transfer programmes in place: 2 for-profit entities (Group1, 40% of respondents), 2 research organisations (Group2, 40%), and 1 other organisation (Group3, CSO, 20%). All for-profit entities with such programmes were SMEs. The item was *S3 Does your organisation have a technology transfer program, or any project related with results transfer?*

In global terms, responses revealed the following results:

Table 43 S3 & S4.1. per group of organisations

	I3-S3 Does your organisation have a technology transfer program, or any project related with results transfer? YES (Counts; n) and % of the (total, N) entities sampled	{ I3-S4.1} Last accounting year investment in euros in technology development and/or transfer Total, €	
Group1. Private for-profit entities	2	40,00%	4.213.812,90 €
Group2. Research Organisations	2	40,00%	10.337.000,00 €
Group3. Other	1	20,00%	- €
Total	5	100,00%	14.550.812,90 €

Source: elaborated by the authors

In terms of investment in technology development and/or transfer during the last accounting year, Group1 (private for-profit entities) invested €4,213,812.90, while Group2 (Research Organisations) invested €10,337,000.00. Group3 reported no investment. The total investment across all groups amounted to €14,550,812.90.

Investment patterns varied significantly, with concentrations primarily in organizations focused on plastics rather than agri-food. Group1 companies account for €5.4 million of total investment, with plastic sector investments being particularly significant. The highest single investment was €4.2 million in the plastic sector by a Group1 entity. The variation in plastic sector investment and its standard deviation indicates significant disparities, suggesting that direct comparisons might be inadequate.

Contextually, the investment in Group1 for-profit entities seems to be significantly greater than the regional reference, being 13,46% (i.e., n=753/5594companies; regional MU) [44], [45]. Comparison between Group2 entities is tough given the fact that research may imply mixed data on technology transfer: evidence in this field is scarce. Group3 organisations investment is also understudied.

Corruption

This impact subcategory assesses whether an organisation has implemented appropriate measures to prevent corruption and if there is evidence that it has engaged or has been engaged in corruption. 8 (57.1%; N=14) organisations responded to have a formal commitment against corruption, *S5 Does the organisation have a formalized commitment to prevent corruption?*. By activity, 5 were private entities (62,5% N=14), 2 were research organisations {Group2} (25%) and 1 was a civil society organisation {Group3} (12.5%).

Poverty alleviation

Responding to the item *S6 Has the organisation carried out in the last accounting year any proactive activity, such as strategies, action plans, investment, to reduce the poverty of the society?*, only 3 organisations provided a positive response (21%; N=14). Information at local or even national level on this investment and socially-responsible actions is scarce and comparable data is not available.

4.3.4.4 Stakeholder category: local community

The mean results and the comparative analysis concerning the actions and impacts addressed to local communities are summarised in the following table:

Table 44 Local community: results and references for comparison

Impact Subcategory	Indicators	Group1: Private for-profit organisations	Group2: Research Organisations	Group3: Other (CSO)	Reference
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Access to material resources	Environmental management system (LC1)	57%	0%	0%	≈1% [42]; MU: 41 Companies SCR system (included)
Access to immaterial resources	Community education initiatives (LC2)	14%	50%	50%	≈13500 students reached by the CEEIM ³⁵ [47]
Delocalization and migration	Immigrant workforce rate (LC3)	10%	0%	0%	58%-77% [23], [48]
	Organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community (LC4)	0%	0%	0%	≈1% [42]; MU: 41 Companies SCR
Cultural heritage	Funding dedicated to support and promote cultural heritage (LC5)	29%	50%	100%	76% [D7.8]
Safe and healthy living conditions	Promotion of community health (LC6)	(6/7) 14%	0%	100%	1 Company BCorp certified in MU [42]
Community engagement	Diversity of community stakeholder groups that engage with the organisation (LC7)	(4/6) 43%	(5/6) 50%	(6/6) 50%	1,48%; MU: 41 Companies SCR system [42]
	Number of meetings with community stakeholders (LC8)	>36	5	175	n.d
	Organisational support (volunteer hours) for community initiatives (LC9)	50	0	2.184	n.d
	Organisational support (financial) (LC9)	17.607,46 €	0	426.176,85 €	
Local employment	Workforce hired locally (LC10)	59%	12%	0%	83% ³⁶ [49, p. 25]
	Spending on locally based suppliers (LC11)	13%	29%	n.d.	80% [D7.8]
Secure living conditions	Security complaints by the community (LC12)	0	0	0	2206 ³⁷ [50]

Source: elaborated by the authors

Access to material resources

³⁵ Non comparable

³⁶ 508612 local (Murcian) workers/ 614838 Total workers (MU, 2023)

³⁷ Non comparable

Organisations may contribute to sustainable development by protecting existing natural resources and their related ecosystem services. With the impact subcategory “Access to material resources” the aim was to assess whether the organisations have a *certified environmental management system (LC1)*. The idea is to take the existence of certified EMS as a proxy for the commitment of companies in a sector to environmental protection. At this final stage of assessment, 57% of organisations of Group1 declared to have a certified EMS. The rest of the organisations in the other groups have declared that they do not have this type of management system.

Access to immaterial resources

This impact subcategory assesses the extent to which organisations respect, work to protect, to provide, or to improve community access to immaterial resources and is measured by the indicator “*community education initiatives*” (LC2). The reason for this indicator relies on the fact that organisations should also transfer knowledge to the community through formal training programs and general community education initiatives [41]. Across the different groups, several organisations declared to have initiatives in place to foster education in the community. Group 1 is the group with the lowest percentage (14%) of entities that reported having carried out this type of activity. In the case of Group 2 and Group 3, 50% of the organisations in both cases stated that they had carried out this type of activity during 2023.

Delocalization and migration

In the case of migrant workers entering a community, the organisation should consider how well workers will integrate with more permanent residents. Organisations should provide opportunities for communication and education between migrant workers and permanent residents. In our case study, just 10% of the organisations in Group1 reported having migrant employees in their workforce. The rest of the groups declared 0%. Moreover, out of this 10% of organisations in Group1, none of them declared to have in place organisational procedures for integrating migrant workers into the community.

Cultural heritage

As a proxy to assess if the organisations promote and preserve cultural heritage, they were asked if they dedicated financial resources to support and promote cultural heritage in the last accounting year (2023) (LC5). 100% of the organisations in Group 3 stated that they have dedicated funding to cultural activities, compared to only 50% in Group 2 and 29% in

Group 1. There is a clear difference between types of organisations in this impact subcategory, being the private for-profit organisations group (Group1) the one with the smallest percentage of organisations providing support to culture.

Safe and healthy living conditions

The indicator established for this impact subcategory has been “*Promotion of community health*” (LC6). Organisations were asked if they dedicated financial resources to strengthen community health in their last accounting year. This includes the general safety conditions of operations and their public health impacts. All the organisations that declared providing support to communities on this aspect were those in Group 3 (100%). In contrast, no organisations in Group 2 expressed any intention to implement these actions, while only 14% of the six respondents in Group 1 indicated plans to deploy such initiatives.

Community engagement

An organisation should attempt to engage with a broad range of stakeholders that represent balanced community interests [41]. To capture the diversity of engaged stakeholders, the organisations were asked to indicate, using a Likert scale, how diverse their engaged stakeholders are, being 1 “*not very diverse*” and 6 “*very diverse*” (LC7). The group that declared to have the more diverse community is Group3 (50% rated the engaged stakeholders with 6/6). It was followed by Group2 (50% of the organisation rated its community with a 5 out of 6). Lastly, 43% of the organisation of Group1 rated its community diversity with a 4 out of 6. Other indicators selected to assess this impact subcategory was “*Number of meetings with community stakeholders*” (LC8). 175 were organised by Group3 in 2023, compared to over 36 had by Group1 and the 5 had by Group2.

Organisations can also foster community engagement through direct involvement in community initiatives (LC9) and/or through financial support (LC10) to this type of projects. Organisational support in this case varies significantly, with Group3 contributing the most in both volunteering hours (2.184) and financial support (426.176,85€), while Group1 provided moderated contributions (50 hours, 17.607,46€), and Group2 reported no support in either category.

Local employment

Local employees have unique knowledge of important community issues and can help the organisation build strong community relations. Furthermore, local employment improves the living conditions of communities, limits the risk of poverty and keeps people from emigrating.

In our analysis, local employment (*LC10*) and local suppliers spending (*LC11*) show significant disparities across organisational groups. Group1 hired the highest percentage of local workers (59%), while Group2 lagged behind (12%), and Group3 reported none. In terms of spending on locally based suppliers, Group2 allocated a higher share (29%) compared to Group1 (13%), though both fell below the reference indicator (80%). This suggests that Group1 contributes more to local employment, whereas Group2 engages more with local suppliers.

Secure living conditions

The objective of this subcategory is to assess if the local community has complained about the organisations practices of private personnel security through the indicator “*security complaints by the community*” (*LC12*). The number of reported complaints in total (considering all the organisations) is 0.

4.3.4.5 Stakeholder category: consumers

The results concerning consumers and the involved organisations are summarised below:

Table 45 Consumers: results and references for comparison

Impact Subcategory	Indicators	Group1: Private for-profit organisations	Group2: Research Organisations	Group3: Other (CSO)	Reference
Health and Safety	Labelling (C1)	(6/6* 1NA) 100%	NA	50%	Mandatory RD 1055/2022 [51]
	Consumer complaints (C2)	544	0	0	Complaints (Total): 3743 ³⁸ [52]
	Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System (C3)	100%	100%	0%	GFSI : ≈15,7% ES (n=6067) [53] ISO 9001 : ES n=30.341 & ISO 22000 : ES n=601 [54]
Feedback mechanism	Presence of consumer feedback mechanism (C4)	(6/7) 71%	(1/2) 0%	0%	GFSI : ≈15,7% ES (n=6067) [53]
Consumer privacy	Consumers' complaints related to breach of privacy (C5)	(6/7) 0	0	0	EU: 1200 ³⁹ attacks to supply chains (general; privacy breaches) [55]
Transparency	Organisation communication transparency (C6)	(6/6) 43%	(4/6) 50%	(6/6) 50%	GFSI : ≈15,7% [53] ISO 9001 : ES n=30.341.

³⁸ Non comparable; most complaints corresponded to telephone and electricity services

³⁹ Non comparable

End-of-life	Internal management systems (C7)	(6/7) 100%	(1/2) 0%	NA	Total:3,2mill (≈1%) [54]
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Source: elaborated by the authors

Health and Safety

This subcategory is composed of three indicators: *C1 Do your products have informative labels? (Labelling)*; *C2 How many consumer complaints has your organisation received in the last accounting year referring to the quality of the commercialised products/services of the organisation? (Consumer complaints)*; *C3 Does your organisation have a Quality and/or Product Safety Management System such as ISO 9001:2015, British Retail Consortium (BRC), Halal, International Food Standard (IFS), ISO 10377:2013, etc.? (Presence of a Quality and/or Product Safety Management system)*. The aim is to identify the existence and scope of systematic efforts to address consumer health and safety across the organisations involved in the life cycle of a product.

Regarding the first indicator (*C1*), all organisations that were asked this question answered ‘Yes’, regardless of the group they belonged to. Consumer complaints (*C2*) are solely recorded in Group1 (544), though still below the total reference (3.743). Lastly, all the organisations both in Group1 and 2 declared to have a Quality and/or Product Safety Quality system. This suggests that private (Group1) and research (Group2) organisations prioritize regulatory compliance, whereas CSOs may face challenges in implementing formal safety and quality management systems.

Feedback mechanism

The right to be heard regarding product and service complaints through communication mechanisms should be included in management measures regarding consumer satisfaction (*C4*). In Group 1, 71% of the organisations (a total of six out of seven organisations responded) confirmed the existence of feedback mechanisms. With regard to Group 2, a single organisation responded, confirming the absence of such mechanisms. In Group 3, none of the organisations reported having any mechanisms in place for consumer feedback.

Consumer privacy

Consumer privacy is particularly affected by the international nature of electronic information, communication and commerce. This subcategory examines whether organisational management systems work to respect and protect consumer privacy. No

complaints related to breach of privacy or loss of data by consumers (C5) were reported in either group.

Transparency

A Likert scale was used to assess organisations' efforts to communicate issues related to their products and social responsibility in a transparent manner to consumers (C6). Being 1 equivalent to “Not very transparent communication” and 6 to “Very transparent communication”, 43% of the organisations in Group1 rated it as “Very transparent”, 50% of organisations in Group2 rated it with 4 out of 6, and in Group3 50% rated it also with a “Very transparent communication”.

End-of-life

In a product life cycle, end-of-life refers to product disposal, reuse or recycling. In an environmental context, this concept is commonly referred to as extended producer responsibility. Product disposal can lead to significant environmental and social concerns. The indicator defined to measure this was “*Internal management systems*” (C7), intended to know if organisations have this type of internal management systems that ensure that clear information is provided to consumers on end-of-life options for products. The results indicate a strong commitment to end-of-life internal management systems among Group1, with 100% of implementation (6 organisations responded out of 7). In contrast, Group2 shows no adoption, while data for Group3 is not available. This suggests that Group1 (private for-profit entities) are more engaged in structured waste and end-of-life product management, whereas Group2 (research organisations) may lack formal systems for handling such processes.

5 Conclusions

The evaluation rationale followed in A2C, based on a two-tier vision (macro and micro), has allowed us to dig deeper into the effects that the project generated in a great variety of actors and stakeholders along the different interventions implemented. This two-tier vision has made it possible to comprehensively examine the socioeconomic, cultural, and acceptability dimensions of the circular economy interventions carried out in A2C.

Macro-level: main conclusions

On the one hand, the macro-level evaluation employed a mixed-methodological framework integrating complementary methodologies from social sciences to capture relevant aspects of circularity such as acceptance, awareness, knowledge transformation and behavioural change mechanisms. The methodological approach incorporated “Theory of Change” conceptualisation, extensive literature review, targeted qualitative interviews, customized qualitative questionnaires and an advanced framework matrix analysis. Notably, the evaluation process was not limited to a single intervention, but it systematically assessed five distinct interventions across six diverse stakeholder groups, ensuring a holistic understanding of the transformative potential of the project.

Significant positive results were found in terms of impact in three critical dimensions (acceptance, awareness and knowledge, and behaviour change). These results varied mainly according to the intervention analysed and the target group analysed. For example, in the Alhama market intervention, the results on the different domains varied between the citizens who completed the survey and the market vendors who participated in the intervention. Notwithstanding the above, one common finding has been that diverse stakeholder groups across multiple activities highlighted a common knowledge gap concerning post-recycling processes—a deficiency that potentially undermines both recycling effectiveness and public motivation to participate. The different gathered views and impacts gave us a holistic approach of the results by area and has allowed to underpin the effectiveness of the interventions. In general terms, all the activities proved to increase the targets’ knowledge and acceptance, although it is true that activities such as mentoring did not have the desired effect for the participants. Finally, it was also identified among the findings the potential for project replication, since the stakeholder overall indicated

substantial receptivity, with initiatives like the Circular Game serving as compelling evidence of the applicability of A2C interventions.

Micro-level: main conclusions

On the other hand, the micro-level evaluation ensured that the sustainability assessment of the technological solution was covered by the LCA methodology, addressing the three dimensions of sustainability, namely, environmental, economic and social. Thus, the micro-level LCA evaluation included an assessment of social impact, identifying key areas requiring organisational improvement: health and safety, social responsibility promotion, delocalization and migration concerns. Regarding health and safety, our analysis identified a potential gap in safety implementation and risk management practices, social responsibility promotion and delocalization and migration, with most organisations lacking concrete policies addressing these issues. These gaps collectively suggest a need for more robust social responsibility frameworks that holistically address community engagement, cultural preservation, and local economic development.

LCC was developed for some of the technologies developed in the project, in particular those involved in demo 3 (high added value substances from agri-food waste by green extraction & ultrasound), demo 4 (high added value extracted substances from agri-food residues by green extraction, enzymatic hydrolysis assisted extraction & microwave) and the plastic chain case study, and several conclusions can be drawn. Both in the case of demo 3 & 4, conventional costs dominate in the fibre and the phenolic extract. Concretely, in the case of demo 3 in the case of fibre the dominant costs are personnel and maintenance, and in the case of phenolic extraction personnel, maintenance and equipment costs have a significant share. Whereas in the case of demo 4, equipment costs are the larger contributors and personnel costs significantly impact fibre cost (*demo output*).

It needs to be highlighted that in both demos, scaling-up the production could generate potential savings, but the recycled products remain more expensive than the conventional alternatives. Despite this current cost differential, continued technological improvements and process optimisations show promising potential to bridge this gap over time, particularly as regulatory frameworks increasingly favour circular economy solutions and market demand for sustainable products grows.

Lastly, regarding the plastic value chain, the main result obtained was that recycling part of the material into pellets decreases both environmental costs and overall economic costs

compared to using only virgin material. This finding underscores the dual benefit of plastic recycling as both an environmentally responsible and economically advantageous approach, providing a strong business case for implementing circular economy principles in plastic manufacturing processes.

Research limitations

This research, however, has methodological limitations. On the social part, a barrier for implementing social LCA in organisations involved in the circular economy is the lack of social performance comparable tools and indicators. Existing tools are limited in their effectiveness by the lack of quantitative data linking social impacts to company operations. The S-LCA methodology, introduced in 2009, remains a nascent approach with limited research application. The SO-LCA variant represents an even more recent development, having been included only in the 2020 edition of existing guidelines. Also, the methodology faces significant constraints that fundamentally limit its comprehensive evaluation potential. The absence of generic databases and the complexity of social data collection further complicate performance tracking and impact assessment. But one of the biggest critical methodological gaps lies in the inability to establish direct cause-effect relationships between technological changes and the evaluated social impacts. Unlike environmental life cycle assessments, the social assessment approach cannot definitively attribute specific social transformations to technological interventions.

In the economic analysis, some methodological limitations should be considered as well. In particular there is no standardised approach to conduct an eLCC analysis for products in the agrifood sector and, the application of eLCC for food products and food waste streams seems to be recent and minimal, if compared to other sectors. The cost of the conventional product, compared with the A2C recycled ones, are estimated on the average market price, by subtracting an estimated price mark up of 30%, which is an assumption reasonable, but not absolutely real for the benchmark. Finally, the methodology to assess the environmental externalities is affected by uncertainty linked to the methods applied to estimate the damage associated with potential environmental impacts. Nevertheless, the methodological choices for conducting the eLCC in A2C have been described in the deliverable making the approach reasoned and replicable.

These methodological challenges highlight the complexity of quantifying social and economic impacts and the importance of developing more sophisticated and consensus-

based assessment tools that can capture the interactions between technological innovations and social systems. In this context, A2C has contributed with relevant case studies and methodologies on SO-LCA and LCC to the urgent need for continued methods and refinement in social and economic life cycle assessment, particularly within CE research.

6 Bibliography

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7 ANNEXES

Annex 1. Framework matrix analysis: interventions social impacts evaluation

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
Circular Game	<p>T01: the method used (video game) seems to have had better results than a lecture (practical vs. theoretical).</p> <p>T01: change in the teachers' perception, from the scepticisms (lack of resources, programming) to the acceptance of the contest.</p>	<p>T01: the activity served to establish teachers existing CE knowledge</p> <p>T01: the existing knowledge (at schools) of the topic is incomplete and theoretical and disconnected from practical actions. Misinformation and lack of familiarity have been identified as barriers.</p> <p>T02: "Not only have we had to teach it, but we have had to learn it too.": thanks to the project they have gained knowledge about CE.</p>	<p>T02: After this experience, the knowledge gained by the teachers is integrated into their daily life.</p> <p>T02: described a transformation in the student's role and behaviour, moving from passive learners to active agents (teaching others and taking responsibility)</p> <p>T02: the participation in this activity has led to change students' perception and attitude (active valuation) towards recycled/ reutilised products.</p>	<p>T01: the activity has potential to be replicable</p> <p>T02: the activity has potential to be replicable (OPINION: it can be successfully replicated, not only for CE)</p> <p>T01: the main activities carried out in the centre are related to materials sorting and local commerce</p> <p>T01: as additional resources to improve teacher practices has</p>

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
		<p>T02: “Students already know these topics and are aware”.</p> <p>RESEARCHER COMMENT: having reviewed T01-T02, both think that students are missing information about the steps that take place after recycling.</p> <p>T02: Lack of public awareness of the impact of recycling and reuse</p> <p>T03: students know the theory, but teachers are not aware if they implement these practices in their day to day</p> <p>T03: the video game has been an interesting activity for them, but the desired effect has not</p>	<p>T02: it was emphasised the need of adopting tools and technologies used by youngsters in the teaching practices</p> <p>T03: confusion in children behaviour since the messages they get from the centre and their home are contradictory</p> <p>T03: the activity hadn’t impacted in children’s behaviour</p> <p>T03: thanks to the game (supposedly) children bring fewer plastic envelopes to school. A change in their attitudes has occurred but this has been an effect achieved through the years + the use of envelopes has been reduced.</p>	<p>been highlighted giving courses to teachers (informative), in order to improve their knowledge about the practices implemented in their environment</p> <p>T02: “This is a pioneering initiative. The degree of involvement has been greater because, not only are we speaking to them in their language with the use of video games, but we are also making them responsible for the training of their classmates. There has never been anything like CIRCULARGAME”.</p> <p>T02: the biggest constraint of CE in education is time</p>

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
		been achieved (not aware of the concept of the CE)		T03: the activity can be easily replicated T03: parents should also be asked to know whether the effect of the activities is the desired or not
ALHAMA MARKET	<p>AP02: Identifying and classifying as CE the activities carried out by market vendors, has reported them satisfaction (recognising that these activities are important, thanks to the project)</p> <p>C0: the 30% of the respondents strongly agree with consuming (<i>I would consume</i>) products made from F&V waste, the 50% agree on it and just the 7% strongly disagree (3% disagree). A 10% neither agree nor disagree</p>	<p>AP02: the vendors are already aware of the concept of CE (maybe not in a theoretical way but yes as an action) and have been implementing some practices independently, such as reusing vegetable waste for livestock or fertiliser.</p> <p>AP02: the AP has an essential role in raising awareness and informing</p> <p>C0: 40% strongly agree that recycled food can be a solution to food waste,</p>	<p>AP02: “work in an activity like this makes you more aware and makes you be much more responsible, even at personal level, at home”</p> <p>AP02: More attention is paid to the organic residues produced by market vendors in the market (by the AP)</p> <p>AP02: observation of a reduced waste after the weekly market, this indicates a tangible shift in behaviour. Even though the selective collection was</p>	<p>AP02: it was recognised the importance of legislation and CE, and the role local development agents could play. However, time and resources constrain were identified as barriers.</p> <p>AP02: expectation for the future: costs savings due to the less amount of waste to collect.</p> <p>AP02: citizens don’t have enough incentives (highlighted the economic ones) to</p>

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly agree are mainly more than 50 years old and women with primary or secondary education - People who strongly disagreed are people aged more than 50, with primary or secondary education <p>C0: 53% of the respondents strongly agree with consuming (<i>I would consume</i>) products that use biodegradable or plant-based plastics. 23% agrees and a 7% strongly disagree</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly agree are mainly women, the age is mixed, and the education profile includes also persons with VET 	<p>and 47% agree. Just the 10% strongly disagree:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly agree are women (10 vs 2) with mixed age and mixed educational level (mainly primary and secondary education) - People who strongly disagree are mainly women (2 vs 1), aged more than 50 with primary & secondary education mainly. <p>C0: 37% strongly agree that biodegradable plastic packaging made from plant waste can help solve pollution problems. The 43% agree, the 17%</p>	<p>not as big as expected, the vendors have responded minimising residues, adopting more responsible waste management practices.</p> <p>AP02: “It is true that, from this, and the awareness that has been raised, it is noticeable that there is less vegetable waste at the weekly market.”</p> <p>C0 (acceptance/ behavioural change): 43% agree on buying (<i>I would buy</i>) products made from fruit and vegetables waste and a 23% totally agree. Just 10% totally strongly disagree. 13% neither agree nor disagree.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly agree are mainly more than 50 years 	<p>make additional efforts. Citizens complain but they carry out the actions, business no because a big investment is needed at the beginning and it prevents them from starting (entrance barrier?)</p> <p>AP02: barrier identified: public servants don’t have the required knowledge to adopt CE practices (time and knowledge are missing)</p> <p>C0: sample characterization → predominantly female, mainly of individuals over 50 years old and has a majority with basic educational levels (primary or secondary)</p>

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly disagree are more than 50 and with primary education <p>RESEARCHER COMMENT: people accept more the products made from plastic than F&V waste (30% vs 53%) (“<i>para comer no, para usar s</i>”)</p> <p>C0Perception: has their perception been improved after seeing the products elaborated from F&V waste?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Strongly agree: 27% - Agree: 63% - Neither agree nor disagree: 7% - Disagree: 3% - Strongly disagree: 0% <p>C0Perception:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Many participants liked the idea and expressed positive attitudes 	<p>neither agree nor disagree, the 0% disagree and the 3% strongly disagree</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - People who strongly agree are women (10 vs 2) with mixed age and mixed educational level (mainly primary and secondary education) <p>C0Perception:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Respondents reported gaining more knowledge and understanding of the products, especially their uses and benefits - Some mentioned they already knew the information 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - old and women with primary or secondary education - People who strongly disagree are more than 50 years old, mainly men with just basic education <p>C0: most carried out actions (at home) to prevent food waste:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Check the fridge/pantry before buying - Consider how food should be stored to keep it fresh - Consider the portion sizes - Using leftovers <p>The least considered action has been: write a food plan</p>	<p>C0: 70% of the respondents didn’t know the A2C project</p> <p>C0: reasons given for consuming or not</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Consume: people are motivated to consume because they help reduce waste, protect the planet, promote sustainability, support health and align with their values for natural and ecological alternatives. Familiarity and seeing progress in product care

Activity	TRIGGERED BY THE PROJECT			
	Acceptance (recognition and approval)	Awareness & knowledge (knowledge of something)	Behavioural changes (action, change of the existing behaviours)	NOTES
	<p>towards the use of products made from food waste</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some believe these products help reduce waste, plastic use, and environmental impact - They appreciate the concept and want it to be practiced more widely <p>MV01: he values the project positively, describing it as a “beautiful initiative” that fosters employment and city cleanliness.</p> <p>MV01: he believes consumers could be willing to pay more for recycled products</p> <p>MV01: criticism of plastic reduction efforts. He perceives this as more of an educational or formative matter, indicating some</p>	<p>presented, but it reinforced their beliefs about sustainability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - A few noted concerns about pesticides, potential waste in production and a lack of clarity regarding some products <p>MV01: he claims to have already been aware of the topic before the project and has neither learned nor improved their knowledge through it.</p> <p>MV01: limited knowledge of the CE beyond A2C practices, its knowledge is mainly focused on individual actions.</p>	<p>C0Perception:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some participants are gradually incorporating these products into their routines, expressing a desire to adopt them “little by little” - Others already practice the concept and are enthusiastic about expanding its use - However, a few indicated that personal barriers, such as age or habits, prevent them from changing their behaviour, even though they like the idea - Specific preferences emerged, such as 	<p>also encourage consumption.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do not consume: high selectiveness, doubts about the product freshness or quality, unclear pricing, or personal preferences against such products. <p>RESEARCHER COMMENT: really different answers between the feedback obtained from the AP and the MV regarding the success of the activity. Alignment between the argument of the AP and MV responses: they are</p>

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	<p>scepticism towards the reduction of plastic in their market places.</p> <p>MV02: supports the continuation and replication of the project since he sees it as very beneficial</p> <p>MV02: notes resistance compared to other regions regarding consuming recycled products:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlights the traditional farming practices dominate due to economic barriers - Perceive higher demand for eco-friendly products abroad, contrasting with local tendencies <p>MV02: economic barriers. Acknowledges that ecological products are more expensive</p>	<p>MV02: limited initial awareness but exposure through the project has clarified the concept.</p> <p>MV03: he claims to have gained understanding, but is attributed to his personal background and habits, not directly to the project.</p>	<p>using these products for cosmetics but not for consumption</p> <p>MV01: The project did not change his behaviour. Neither did consumers.</p> <p>MV01: he believes these practices should expand in the future (favourable attitude towards future change, although no current actions are evident).</p> <p>MV02: notes resistance to ecological practices due to adherence to traditional farming methods and their higher costs associated</p> <p>MV03: notes a shift in consumers preferences towards high-quality but smaller quantities of product. Rejection of</p>	<p>carrying out CE practices and think that are important but are not aware of the name itself. Really willing to make more activities like this one.</p> <p>RESEARCHER COMMENT: market vendors link the CE just with recycling. The main two activities mentioned are recycling at home and the fact that people go to the market with their own bags.</p>

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	<p>and less accessible, which hinders widespread adoption despite the perceived increased environmental awareness</p> <p>MV03: observes a generational division in sustainable behaviour</p> <p>MV03: notes an increase in consumers bringing their own bags, but believes broader changes are gradual and will take time to be fully manifested</p> <p>MV03: he strongly supports the expansion of these practices (long-term potential)</p>		<p>visual imperfect F&V (impact in price??)</p>	
<p>MENTORING PROGRAMME (N=2)</p>	<p>B01: The programme effectiveness has been rated as 6/10. Benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expansion of contacts for future projects 	<p>B01: the mentoring programme raised awareness among workers</p> <p>B01: Satisfaction with the mentoring programme in terms of increasing</p>	<p>B01: More positive attitudes/behaviours towards circular economy products in their business,</p> <p>B01: Increased willingness to pay for reused products in their business practices</p>	<p>RESEARCHER COMMENT: More information available but not DIRECTLY related with the project.</p>

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	- Organisation of work to be more efficient	awareness and CE practices acceptance: 6,5	(i.e. value chain inputs, service providers...),	
DEMO VISIT (N=9)		<p>DEMO01: The visit has improved their knowledge regarding practical methods to reduce food & plastic waste:</p> <p>Not improved at all (1): 7%</p> <p>Slightly improved (2): 13%</p> <p>Moderately improved (3): 20%</p> <p>Improved (4): 27%</p> <p>Significantly improved (5): 33%</p> <p>How:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - No previous knowledge of the method - Test on a pilot scale what is done in the laboratory 		<p>DEMO01:</p> <p>9 respondents: 6 M & 3 F,</p> <p>78% of the respondents thinks that some of the results presented in the visit can be applied to their activity</p> <p>Useful results:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cell disruption for purification processes - plant equipment - obtaining polyphenol-rich fractions for use as antioxidants - Compound extraction

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Knowledge on the extraction methods/ processes - Improve the practical knowledge of the technologies used for waste valorisation <p>DEMO01: Exchange with peers about topics related to the demo:</p> <p>Nothing relevant (1): 0%</p> <p>Not very relevant (2): 11%</p> <p>Moderately relevant (3): 0%</p> <p>Quite relevant (4): 44%</p> <p>Very relevant (5): 33%</p> <p>DEMO01: Why this knowledge would be useful for their peers:</p>		

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Waste valorisation alternatives - The availability of equipment in which the whole process can be carried out a larger scale than the laboratory is of great interest in circular bioeconomy projects - R+D collaboration 		
B01: By-product management and R&I for new products (N=8)		<p>B01: Tangible benefits/ results identified in companies after the collaboration with A2C:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The two preferred options were: improved customer satisfaction (27%) and non-benefits at all (27%). 	<p>B01: The project has improved the quality, production or R&D department of the companies. One company also states that it has contributed to restructure their work in daily operations. One company stated that the activities</p>	<p>B01:</p> <p>40% know the project mainly thanks to the website</p> <p>20% raw materials supplier</p> <p>20% Attendance to dissemination events</p> <p>10% Attendance to stakeholders' meetings</p>

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Then: increased efficiency (18%) and influenced more positive attitudes/behaviours towards circular economy products in your business (18%) • One respondent stated that “<i>it generated discomfort in some workers</i>” <p>B01: The 62% of responders stated that A2C activities have not improved their compression of CE</p>	had no influence in their activity.	10% Participating in the mentoring programme
WORKERS	<p>NEP analysis (awareness).</p> <p>General comments:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The average has increased from 48,78 to 55,56, which suggest a change towards values more aligned with a pro environmental view 			

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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limits to growth: increased from 2,95 to 3,06, indicating a slightly higher awareness of growth limits (small change). SD decreased (less variability) ○ Antianthropocentrism: increase in the mean from 3,36 to 3,86, what reflects a stronger rejection of an anthropocentric worldview ○ Fragility of nature’s balance: increased from 3,84 to 3,88 → showing stability in the perception that nature is fragile (the SD decreased indicating a better consensus in this dimension) ○ Rejection of exemptionalism: decreased from 3,31 to 3,22. This might indicate a reduced willingness to reject the idea that humans are exceptional and not subject to natural laws. ○ Possibility of an Eco-crisis: mean decreased slightly from 3,79 to 3,70 à slightly lower perfection of the likelihood of an ecological crisis <p>The results suggest a generally positive effect of the intervention</p>			
<i>General comments</i>	<p>AP01: Acceptance of the sustainability voucher by A2C finalist companies positively rated (recognition and approval)</p> <p>AP01: companies have expressed interest in the CE, this derived in the creation of a CE practices map of the Region of Murcia and a dynamic catalogue of good practices</p>	<p>AP01: Acknowledgement and identification of the importance of company feedback as key benefit of the project.</p> <p>AP01: lack of awareness of the public administration. Missing actions not in place (mainly related with the availability and facility of recycling infrastructures)</p>	<p>AP01: Personal behavioural change (perspectives & activities) through participation in the project</p> <p>AP01: change in mindset and practice of companies, thanks to an improved attitude coupled with the adoption of new practices demonstrates a concrete shift in behaviour. This change is</p>	<p>AP01: example of good practice in implementing CE is the sustainability voucher created by INFO</p>

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			triggered at some extent by the regulation.	

Annex 2. Materials

In case the reader would like to have access to the templates of the different information gathering materials presented in the document, please contact amatamoros@kveloce.com